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**Regional News Writing in the Digital Age: A Narrative Inquiry into the Practices
of Filipino Journalists in Western Visayas**

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REGIONAL NEWS WRITING IN THE DIGITAL AGE: A NARRATIVE INQUIRY INTO THE PRACTICES OF FILIPINO JOURNALISTS IN WESTERN VISAYAS

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Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **GEFF B. SAGALA** with the title: **REGIONAL NEWS WRITING IN THE DIGITAL AGE: A NARRATIVE INQUIRY INTO THE PRACTICES OF FILIPINO JOURNALISTS IN WESTERN VISAYAS** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree Doctor of Communication.

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Biographical Sketch

I am Mr. Geff B. Sagala, currently working and living in Iloilo City, the City of Love. I now work as an AB Communication Faculty member at the University of San Agustin, Iloilo City. Consequently, I am also the Institute Coordinator of the University for Humanities and Social Sciences. I have years of experience teaching major subjects in Communication and general education courses in Humanities, Education, and Research Writing. I am a published researcher with collaborative work with both students and colleagues.

For my educational background, I graduated with a Bachelor of Science in Chemical Engineering minor in Management at Mapua Institute of Technology (now Mapua University) in 2005. I obtained my Master's degree in Development Communication at the University of the Philippines - Open University in 2019 and got Chancellor's List recognition.

For my work experiences, I was previously affiliated with different colleges in Bacolod City before transferring to Iloilo City. Before 2019, I was an Overseas Filipino Worker in Saudi Arabia from 2009 until 2019. I worked as Senior Corporate Procurement Officer before pursuing my passion for teaching. Aside from this, I also have years of experience in the field of Sales, Marketing, and Business Development.

For my hobbies, I am a Distinguished Toastmaster (DTM) with years of experience in public speaking and community leadership. I also love traveling and outdoor activities such as hiking and trekking.

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Dedication

I want to dedicate this scholarly work to my three incredible nieces and nephew, Hace, Haley, and Sky. I pray that this will inspire the three of you to be passionate in your calling and never stop pursuing your dreams.

Moreover, this academic achievement is for my lovely mother, Marylene, who deserves all the love in the world for her boundless love for her children.

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Regional News Writing in the Digital Age: A Narrative Inquiry into the Practices of Filipino Journalists in Western Visayas

The world of journalism is constantly evolving alongside social reality to where it belongs. Thus, it is vital to understand the experiences of journalists in news writing and narrate their practices as they catch up with the increasing demands of the public. Through this study, media practitioners and educators can understand the current practices of Filipino journalists and the influences in news writing in Western Visayas. Nine local journalists participated in an online in-depth interview resulting to the discussion of (1) journalistic practices in the new media, (2) practices that implicate objectivity in news writing, (3) assessment of the hierarchy of influence model in the news writing process, and (4) news writing framework. Results showed that the news writing process has evolved because of the emergence of new media. Technology and mobile devices revolutionized the news writing process, which involves gathering, writing, and selecting news content. Moreover, this study concludes that the emergence of new media considerably impacted objectivity in news writing and has a significant influence in the practices of multimedia journalists.

Keywords: Journalism, Multimedia Journalists, Narrative Inquiry, Western Visayas

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Rationale and Background of the Study

Journalism, in its core, sits on the belief that its proponents should accurately report on social issues (Shapiro, 2017; Burns & Matthews, 2018) and generally be concerned about the lives of ordinary people (Hölsgens et al., 2020; Iggers, 2018). According to Smaniotto (2020), investigative journalism respects facts as the primary underpinning of discussions. Meanwhile, the United Nations (UN) emphasizes that media should promote democracy, dialogue, and development (Hanitzsch et al., 2019).

Traditionally, journalists gather facts, write a story, and then distribute it to the public through media outlets (Maniou et al., 2020). Journalists actively participate in creating the news, its content, and its distribution (Hellmueller & Mellado, 2015; Vos et al., 2019). Before news stories are published, journalists must interpret and develop them as captivating articles (Carter, 2013; Baden & Tenenboim-Weinblatt, 2018).

News can be defined as anything that changes the status quo (Russial et al., 2015). The opinions of media professionals about national and international news and policies are attributed to news writing. According to Van Dijk (2013), the news is new information about current events, things, or people that is broadcast on the radio, television, or written in the newspaper. Over time, however, and due to the progress of digital media, the news is becoming increasingly prevalent on social media. As a result of this development, news organizations have invested in social media to disseminate news materials (Hermida et al., 2012). Shearer and Gottfried's

2017 survey showed that 67 percent of Americans access social media news. Even the Philippine media have gone global, as seen by the media outlets having online versions (Maslog et al., 2015).

Due to the advent of social media, where content is self-generated, fake news stories have gone viral not only because of the internet but more so of the under-supervised release of unverified news (Lazer et al., 2018). Hence, the birth of trolls, fake news, and misinformation threatens freedom and democracy in the Philippines (Ong & Tapsell, 2022). Lees (2018) claimed that political leaders, including those in the Philippines, use fake news to undermine factual news reporting, target journalists, and sow discord in the media.

Journalists report on current events and produce news to raise people's awareness of various societal issues. Gever (2019) and Opperhuizen et al. (2019) suggested numerous factors, from inner to extrinsic incentives, and how this affects journalists' story creation. Furthermore, Schuck et al. (2016) stated that news organizations emphasize stories that interest their audience. The news media use various techniques to present the general issue while focusing on specific topics or arguments (Geçer & Mahinay, 2018). According to Ardèvol-Abreu (2015), news stories concentrate on details and are already constrained windows of perceived reality.

Thus, one may wonder how journalists write stories with the onset of the new media. Hence, the study aimed to understand news writing by describing the various practices of Filipino journalists, specifically in Western Visayas, through a narrative inquiry approach. Narratives are daily accounts that glimpse one's life story (Daiute, 2013). This study delved into Filipino journalists' personal experiences of writing news stories leading to the development a framework for their journalistic practice in

Western Visayas. It focused on the journalistic process of gathering, selecting, and producing news among these journalists.

Western Visayas, commonly known as Region VI, is one of the 18 administrative regions in the Philippines and the fifth-largest regional economy outside the National Capital Region (NCR) (Nagaynay & Lee, 2020). Region VI consists of three main landmasses with six provinces, namely, Aklan, Antique, Capiz, Iloilo, Guimaras, and Negros Occidental (Roxas & Fillone, 2016). Umali (2013) found that news stories in Western Visayas are heavily patterned from news produced in the NCR. Moreover, Ladera and Lebrilla (2012) said that the majority of the media companies in Western Visayas use no definite and professional broadcast techniques.

Literature describing the different journalistic practices in news production is already abundant in media studies. Brüggemann (2014) mentioned that journalists write stories in line with their interpretations. Van Dalen et al. (2012) highlighted the differences in journalists' role conceptions and news reporting style. Opiniano et al. (2021) also observed how Filipino journalists reflect on their news work to improve their news writing skills and work values.

These previous studies established the role of journalists in news production. However, understanding and describing the practices of Filipino journalists, specifically in Western Visayas, has not been investigated yet. This study assumes the world of journalism as a muted voice. "Voice" refers to unique perspectives often silenced or misunderstood (Putnam, 2001; Saludadez, 2021).

Understanding news writing and how journalists write stories in the digital age is essential. According to Mensing (2010), traditional media's impact is already waning because news is individualized. With this, journalists must stay relevant and

readjust their journalistic practices to meet the public's demands. This study then theorized Filipino journalists' practices and developed a framework depicting the process of writing news stories. Eventually, results could help media organizations and journalism educators reconsider journalistic practices in news production, embracing the new challenges in journalism in Western Visayas and the country.

Statement of the Problem

Journalism is constantly evolving alongside social reality to where it belongs. Thus, it is vital to understand the experiences of journalists in news writing and narrate their practices as they catch up with the increasing demands of the public. Through this study, media practitioners and educators can understand the current practices of Filipino journalists in news writing in Western Visayas. Given that the landscape in news reporting has shifted from gatekeeping to largely user-generated content, how can truth be reported accurately? The shift in how the news is written presumably is greatly affected by personal rather than objective views of reporting. The time to produce content, especially with new media as a platform, is much faster than traditional reporting. The internet undeniably makes the spread of fake news faster with a broader audience reach (Cruz et al., 2019). The process could then compromise objectivity and reveal what is true. In effect, readers can be misled or misinformed.

The weaponization of fake news in the Philippines is often systematic and involves the mobilization of troll armies and the production of inaccurate content (Tandoc, 2022). With this strategic move to spread misinformation through fake news, relevant laws are already enacted in different countries, including the Philippines. However, fact-checking fake news remains daunting amidst these

actions and still poses a massive threat to journalism (Cha et al., 2020) and journalists.

Similarly, Harcup (2012) posited that news production, reporting, and reception are changing. The internet implicates the world of journalism and shakes its institution to the core. Shapiro (2014) even articulated that the speed of journalism transformation is almost dizzying, requiring swift action and response. Journalists must cope with the demands of the public to stay significant to the society on which the study is grounded.

Generally, this study attempted to answer the research question, "With the advent of the new media, how news writing among Filipino journalists in Western Visayas is shaped?"

Specifically, this study answered the following research questions:

- a) What are the journalistic practices of news writers in Western Visayas, and how it plays in the news writing process?
- b) How do these practices implicate objectivity in news writing?
- c) What levels in the hierarchy of influences are still enacted in the news writing process in the digital age? and
- d) What news writing framework can be derived from the practices of Filipino journalists in Western Visayas?

Objectives of the Study

In general, the study analyzed how Filipino journalists in Western Visayas write news with the advent of the new media.

Specifically, this study aimed to:

- a) Find out the journalistic practices of news writers in Western Visayas and their interplay in the news writing process;
- b) Explain how these practices implicate objectivity in news writing;
- c) Assess the hierarchy of influences enacted in the news writing process in the digital age. and
- d) Develop a news writing framework derived from the practices of Filipino journalists in Western Visayas.

Significance of the Study

Various literature recorded the role of journalists in news production (Lecheler & De Vreese, 2019; Bartholomé et al., 2018). However, Filipino journalists' practices in news writing in Western Visayas have not been explored and described yet. It is crucial to describe how journalists produce news stories that are relevant and interesting to inform the public about what is happening around them.

The results of this study are not limited to the journalists. Understanding their life experiences in news writing may give a glimpse of the current journalistic practices in this region. Given the changing communication landscape, this study could help practicing journalists understand other journalists' motivations in news production.

Moreover, this study may also be beneficial to media organizations. It could help them understand journalists' personal experiences and review news production's journalistic practices in Western Visayas. This may also help media organizations assess the current media landscape and how news production stays relevant in shaping society.

Finally, this study may also benefit communication scholars and practitioners by giving a glimpse into the journalistic practices in Western Visayas. This could also help the academic community provide real-life situations on news production.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The locale of the study was confined to Western Visayas. However, not all journalists formed part of the study, although, each province is represented. Results may not be generalizable, and findings limited. This will however give a glimpse of the journalistic practices in a locale far from NCR which is seen as the center of news reporting. The study also did not investigate the kinds or types of news that they report on nor investigated their writing style.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Al Nahed and Hammond (2018) pointed out that journalistic practices differ significantly in their procedures, emphasis, and assumptions. Journalists sometimes intervene in news production by using an interpretative approach that focuses on the meaning of events that go beyond facts and sources (Falasca, 2014) which may also be applicable in the Philippines.

Philippine Journalism

The evolving news landscape challenges Philippine journalism, with corresponding criticisms threatening its credibility. Even so, Balod and Hameleers (2021) said Filipino journalists perceived their profession as the defender of truth and advocates of societal reform. Filipino journalists see their crucial role in guarding democracy in the country. The journalists' perception of their role in news production has a massive impact on media content production (Bartholomé et al., 2015). More so, Prager and Hameleers (2021) highlighted that media play a significant role in forming public opinion.

Skovsgaard et al. (2012) articulated that journalists perform an active and participative role in societal affairs as political watchdogs. The news process determines the thematic categories facilitating public discussion (Bennett & Pfetsch, 2018). However, according to Tandoc et al. (2012), certain factors, such as editorial decisions, other functions, and media pressures, can impede the performance of this role in the Philippine journalism landscape.

Aside from these challenges, Filipino journalists are also concerned with low pay, violence targeting journalists, information access, and professionalism (Tandoc, 2017). In fact, according to Aguilar et al. (2014), the Philippines had the most murdered journalists between 1992 and 2012. This report perceives that the country does not enjoy total press freedom because of the lingering threat to journalists. Moreover, Tandoc et al. (2021) highlighted that women journalists in the Philippines encounter online harassment more often than their male counterparts, and still ongoing even on digital platforms.

Since the Philippines is also one of the consumers of digital media, it paved the way for the rise of fake news and disinformation. Fake news deliberately beguiles the public to accept false and biased ideologies (Fernandez & Devaraj, 2019). According to Ragragio (2021), fake news disfigures free expression and press freedom. Unfortunately, Deinla et al. (2022) study said that the youth in the Philippines were less likely to identify news between real and fake.

Additionally, a Social Weather Stations (SWS) survey found that 51 percent of Filipinos cannot spot fake news (Tuquero, 2022). This implies that news in social media is rampant and trusted by the public, with an increased risk of vulnerability to being fake. The public can be misinformed about current events because of their inability to detect fake news.

News and Political Communication

According to Davis (2014), citizens need information about current affairs for democracy to be well-functioning. The public needs crucial knowledge to make sound decisions about their lives and society. The focus of democratic institutions assumed a well-functioning public sphere in which communication from media

organizations can influence and shape the opinions and actions of the people (Bennett & Pfetsch, 2018). According to (Leong, 2015), media is a public space for groups and individuals to express their views and exchange arguments and conversations until the truth emerges. Presenting specific topics and directing the public attention to themes implicates social discourse (Ceron et al., 2016; Reyes-Sosa et al., 2020). Atkinson et al. (2014) found that issue salience in a major news organization was crucial to developing a robust national agenda.

Journalism is crucial in maintaining balance within politics and democratic society (Andresen et al., 2017; Schroeder, 2022). The most prominent concern is the issue of news media agendas and public affairs (McCombs et al., 2014). However, according to McNair (2017), the expanding globalized public sphere and digital media network have transformed political communication allowing political actors to bypass traditional, established media in communicating with the public. Blumler (2015) revealed that new media politicians reached audiences without journalistic intervention with diversified content and voice shaping public opinion. These political communication and media revolutions transformed society's decisions in making the right choices, especially in politics.

Ekman and Widholm (2015) said politicians had adopted social media to express their standpoint about a particular issue and compete with other political figures. Politicians can now directly convey their message to the public and discuss societal issues. Politicians use the news to criticize other politicians, while journalists cover and report political tensions (Van der Goot, 2022). However, political disputes foster viewpoint polarization (Van Aelst et al., 2017), making citizens less attached to politics (Bennett & Iyengar, 2008). Additionally, online misinformation implicates democracy by manipulating candidates and policymaking that affects ordinary

people (Colomina et al., 2021). Aside from this, politicians have started resorting to fake news and hate speech integrated into their political messages aiming to misinform, disinform, and malinform the public (Oparaugo, 2021).

The media environment and political communication systems evolved primarily due to the proliferation of new media (Vowe & Henn, 2016). Journalists reported the political conflict to represent political reality and showcase politicians' differing viewpoints (Van der Goot, 2022; Lecheler & De Vreese, 2019). International relations news reports affected government policies and public opinions (Burrett, 2014). With more people relying on social media as their source of political news stories, biased content could influence the public, especially if they cannot distinguish truth from facts or news from propaganda (Oparaugo, 2021).

Moreover, according to Bjarnøe et al. (2020), citizens who gain information by consuming news can participate more actively in politics. Attributes, judgments, and decisions of the public are suggested and heavily influenced by news stories. Mendoza et al. (2022) opined that the quality of information online through news stories matters for Filipino voters deciding to vote. Regardless of their credibility, online news stories increase the likelihood of Filipino youths participating in the local and national elections. The study of Arugay and Baquisal (2022) argued that social media was critical in the production, transmission, and reception of election-related information and narratives that resulted in online polarization and mobilization of Filipino voters in the 2022 elections.

News in Digital Media

Mass media is still the primary source of information on current affairs (Newman et al., 2016). However, most people have smartphones and other digital

devices where they can read, access, and share news stories anywhere. The age of digital media revolutionized almost every aspect of journalism (Franklin, 2014). The boundaries between professionals, citizens, and activists are divided by how news is generated and received in the digital age (García-Orosa et al., 2020).

Digitization is one of the primary movers in the evolution of journalism. Chan (2014) argued that digital media had changed journalism practices and revolutionized news values, professional ethics, and newsroom management. Aside from this, digital media also posed a massive challenge to newspaper businesses and established news media organizations that challenged local and international media industries (Nielsen, 2015).

Similarly, Blake (2019) said that how news and information are disseminated in the digital age has altered how it is presented, including linguistic style, perspective, and word choice. Additionally, Kim and Dennis (2019) opined that the presentation format of highlighting the source also affects the public. News that highlights its source makes a good impression regardless of the source's credibility. Such strategies make other news articles less attractive to the readers.

On the other hand, Hong and Nadler (2015) found that social media democratized how people consume news by selecting their preferred type of information to read. Due to social media, the public is even participating in producing news themselves (Yang & Su, 2020), which implicates the world of professional journalism. According to Miller (2019), citizen journalism has upended news and media landscapes by undermining the objectivity and fairness of information from mainstream media to media newsrooms. This phenomenon alerted the journalism field and communication scholars to reassess what constitutes news and the news

writers. However, Örnebring (2013) articulated that journalists have more expertise, authority, and professionalism than amateur writers producing news stories.

With the proliferation of digital media, the emergence of new genres of journalism came into the picture (Franklin, 2014). One of these genres is narrative devices dependent on mainstream journalism (Horbyk et al., 2021). Fake news is imitations, hijacked, and integrated forms of mainstream media storytelling. Even so, the public will not blindly believe the news even if they are reported by media organizations (Vargo et al., 2018). Research also suggests that journalists still check their reports with peers and other established media organizations to validate the accuracy of their news stories (McCombs, 2014). These network relationships between news items and information can be transmitted from the media to the public's mind (Guo & McCombs, 2016) based on the degree of importance to the receivers, which can be explained by Shoemaker and Reese's hierarchy of influence model (2013).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Thus, the study was anchored on Shoemaker and Reese's Hierarchy of Influence model (2013). This theoretical framework includes five levels describing various factors affecting news content, including the routines influencing media's journalistic activity. The five levels of influence include social systems, social institutions (outside the media organization), media organizations, routine practices, and individuals. The hierarchy of influence model may aid in understanding the various influences that shape news content at all levels, from the individual to the social system (Reese, 2016).

This framework posits that individual characteristics are at the very core of the hierarchy of influences. Individual level refers to the person's personality traits, values, and beliefs affecting their practices. Theoretically, journalists' attitude, education, and experience impact their reporting habits (Reese, 2001). Although individual characteristics are assumed to abide by the pursuit of objective reporting, various media studies proved that personal biases matter (Reese, 2019) and are reflected in journalists' news stories. Willnat et al. (2013) recognized demographic characteristics such as age, gender, education level, and employment history and personal characteristics like political views and family values (Patterson & Donsbach, 1996) as some of the factors affecting the practices of the journalists at the individual level (Milojević & Krstić, 2018). Additionally, Hughes et al. (2016) contend that in emerging democracies, severe social inequities and financial constraints significantly impact journalists' jobs.

The routine level concerns the behavioral patterns that make up the immediate structures of media production, such as implicit rules and ritualized enactments that aren't necessarily made clear (Milojević & Krstić, 2018). Policies, laws, and customs firmly hold how journalism is practiced worldwide. Routines are predictable behaviors that help us perceive and behave in the social world (Reese, 2001). Journalists must work within various constraints imposed by technology, time, place, and customs and are not free to act on their thoughts and attitudes. However, in some circumstances, journalism practices can instill problematic behavior. Relly et al. (2015) highlighted that most journalists had no ethical issues paying a source for information. Moreover, the culture of corruption in media was observed to impact the world of journalism as journalists are susceptible to accepting small bribes affecting their news outputs.

Digital news editors, managers, and media owners are recognized to have a massive influence on journalism at the organizational level (Reese, 2019). The organizational level is aware that news is produced by organizations with their own economic and political priorities (Milojević & Krstić, 2018). However, organizations must recognize that they are crucial in balancing journalism's commercial and professional aspects. The organizational level should take into account the requirements that give rise to the routine levels and how people are required to interact with one another within that more substantial formal structure (Reese, 2001). The most pressing concern at the organizational level is the decision-makers influencing the news production and writing process. According to Jungblut and Hoxha (2016), interventions by media owners and editors, primarily due to political or economic reasons, significantly impacted journalist self-censorship.

Another level called the extra-media level, that influences journalism is rooted in social institutions outside the media organization, such as government, advertisers, public relations, influential political figures, interest groups, and other media organizations (Reese, 2001). Reese and Shoemaker (2016) emphasized that the extra-media level is the interplay of economic, political, and cultural factors connecting the organization's relationship and society. It suggests that the extra-media level shadows the responsibility to shape news content with the journalists. However, this level posits that elite interests in the more extensive system through corporate media organizations hamper the credibility and authority of the world of journalism.

Lastly, the concept of more significant, more complex systems within which journalism operates is captured at the social systems level (Milojević & Krstić, 2018). A nexus of interdependencies between business, politics, and the media is created

by the strongest inter-organizational ties and observation of the media's role in the greater social distribution of power (Reese, 2019). In transitional media systems, persisting power structures and historical legacies influence the structural conditions of journalism (Lohner et al., 2017). At this level, journalism can be seen as a component of an organic, sociocultural totality that includes some critical examination of news. Additionally, this enables a universal viewpoint outside of the more conventionally culturally constrained job of ideological analysis (Milojević & Krstić, 2018).

Shoemaker and Reese (1996) contextualized influences within an appealing conceptual framework that helped explore where news comes from. According to Reese (2019), a better understanding of the individual agency and the organization is necessary to grasp how an individual acts within larger social, economic, and political structures. The hierarchy of influence explains how media content is influenced by everything from macrosystem-level ideologies and other variables to more individualized media persons (Shoemaker & Reese, 1996).

This framework is appropriate for understanding the journalistic practices involved in news production and media content. Reese (2001) articulated that the hierarchy of influence can help clarify and address issues concerning the factors shaping media and news content. The journalists' work practices, news routines, organizational, extra-media, and ideological perspectives can affect the news content. Moreover, the hierarchy of influence model can consider the larger structure within the journalists' function. Even though new media configurations may emerge in the network public sphere, emerging spaces can be understood within a broader power structure (Reese, 2016).

Various communication scholars also used this framework to understand the different journalistic practices involved in media content. For instance, Kwanda and Lin (2020) also used the Hierarchy of Influence Model to examine news organization information patterns and journalistic practices during the 2018 Palu earthquake and tsunami. The study showed that individual journalistic expertise was essential when dealing with fake news reports, and some local techniques were different from Western media methods. Moreover, news professionals prefer to present balanced reporting at the routine level. At the same time, independent media treat the government as the authority to refute risky, controversial fake news.

Similarly, Fahmy and Johnson (2012) assessed how effectively embedded journalists felt they covered the Iraq War and whether these perceptions have evolved. The study found that professional values and norms were essential in reporting the conflict. In contrast, embedded reporters cited individual-level issues, extra-media influences, and ideological elements as having a more significant impact on their reporting.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This qualitative study used a narrative inquiry study design. Qualitative research mainly focuses on people's experiences (Silverman, 2020) which has a wide-ranging domain that uses various data collection and analysis methods (Wilson & Anagnostopoulos, 2021). Qualitative studies are generally written texts, usually transcriptions of individual interviews or focus group discussions, that seek to understand the meaning of one's personal experience (Grossoehme, 2014).

Meanwhile, a narrative inquiry study primarily investigates understanding life experiences and describing their meaning. According to Lindsay et al. (2016), experiences are reflected and reconstructed to reveal the construction of reality. Moreover, as per Creswell (2013), narrative research is rooted in different social and humanities disciplines.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in Western Visayas, where the participants work as journalists. Western Visayas or commonly known as Region VI, has six provinces, namely, Aklan, Antique, Capiz, Iloilo, Guimaras, and Negros Occidental. It is located in the central part of the Philippines, within the Visayas group of islands. The region boasts numerous tourist destinations, historical sites, and natural landscapes. Amongst the top tourist destination is the internationally acclaimed Boracay Island, located in Aklan (Nagaynay & Lee, 2020).

Participants of the Study

This study investigated the multiple perspectives of Filipino journalists in Western Visayas via an in-depth one-on-one interview to learn about their journalistic practices in news writing.

Nine (9) Filipino journalists in Western Visayas who met the following inclusion criteria were interviewed:

- 1) Working as a news writer affiliated with a local media outlet in Western Visayas for more than five years;
- 2) Has extensive experience in writing news in the Philippines;
- 3) Has experience in any of the following fields: investigative, watchdog, broadcast, online, opinion, or political journalism; and
- 4) Has experience in both traditional and digital newsrooms

Data Gathering Procedure

A series of in-depth interviews (dialogical process) was conducted. This method was the most common practice for capturing journalists' experiences and multiple views (Iorio, 2014). All interviews were conducted via Zoom from February 16 to 25, 2023. The interviews lasted 40 to 68 minutes and were recorded for documentation and transcription.

Data Analysis

Thematic coding was employed to analyze the transcribed interview using Braun and Clarke's (2006) systematic method of capturing themes or patterns. Analysis of the experiences yields to identifying overarching themes described by the participants (Dawadi, 2021).

First, familiarize with the data by reading and re-reading the transcripts. As Maguire & Delahunt (2017) articulated, it is imperative to be familiar with the entire body of data or data corpus before proceeding with the next step.

Second, initial codes were developed to organize the data meaningfully and systematically. This study intended to have an inductive analysis; hence, it used line-by-line coding to code every statement of the participants. Data were collated into groups identified as codes. These codes resulted in a condensed overview of the primary data and shared meanings.

Third, patterns or initial themes significant to the research question were identified. The data that closely fit together was considered as initial themes. At the end of this step, the initial codes were organized into broader themes relevant to the research question.

Fourth, initial themes were reviewed and clustered similar data together. Themes should be coherent and distinct from each other.

Fifth, final themes in discussing the findings were developed. Defining themes involves formulating precisely what each theme means and figuring out how it can help understand each theme's name.

Lastly, a significant and relevant report on the research question was written. A thematic analysis requires an introduction to establish the research question, aims, and approach.

Rigors of the Study

In any qualitative research study, it is vital to establish the plausibility or trustworthiness of the study (Cloutier & Ravasi, 2021), that is, confidence that it followed a rigorous process of collecting and analyzing research data (Reinhardt et

al., 2018) and presented the findings grounded in empirical evidence (Pratt et al., 2020). This research will utilize Lincoln and Guba's (1986) rigor of the study, including credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability.

Credibility establishes that the information and findings of the study are credible and provide confidence that this is factual. In this research, credibility was established via *member-checking*. This strategy ensured that findings were rich, robust, comprehensive, and well-developed. It asked the participants to check and verify the results to confirm the plausibility of the findings.

Transferability refers to how the findings can be transferred to other contexts with other participants (Maher et al., 2018). This was established via *thick description and purposive sampling techniques*. It was ensured that all pertinent information was captured with a detailed account of the participant's experiences and opinions about the research variables. This research also employed a purposive sampling technique to identify the participants and their credentials, making them qualified to share their views about the research topic. This ensured that the participants provided rich and full of factual information.

Dependability refers to how other researchers can repeat the study but still have the same findings or consistent results (Kyngäs et al., 2020). This was ensured via *code recode*. A two-week interval was observed in coding and processing themes in the code-recode process. Given the time interval, a consistent result for the final theme ensued.

Confirmability is the degree to which the results of an inquiry can be corroborated or confirmed by other researchers (Elo et al., 2014). This means that all findings can be confirmed via proper documentation and are not just a figment of the researcher's imagination. This was ensured via an *audit trail*. Permission was sought

from the participants to record the entire interview for proper documentation. This was also used for transcribing the full interview and thematic analysis.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are one of the essential parts of research. It is an integral aspect of research that must remain at our work's forefront. All information was treated confidential and private, including protecting human subjects, using the research data for academic purposes only, ensuring equality, and avoiding prejudice and harassment.

Participants were provided an informed consent form indicating their willingness to participate in this study voluntarily. The informed consent form included the study's purpose, interview duration, procedure, and risks. It also stated certain conditions, such as not having incentives or compensation and the right to withdraw or refuse to participate without consequences.

Participants were informed about the confidentiality and anonymity of their statements in the interviews by using password-protected interview recordings, using coded aliases instead of their actual names during the data analysis, and discarding the data after the completion of the study.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nine Filipino journalists working in Western Visayas participated as participants (P) and served as the primary sources of information. There were six female and three male journalists who participated in this study. They have extensive experience in the newsroom ranging from 10 to 39 years. Their profile shows they have in-depth knowledge of traditional and new media. Their names and media organizations were hidden for confidentiality (Table 1).

All interviews were conducted via Zoom from February 16 to 25, 2023. The interviews lasted 40 to 68 minutes and were recorded for documentation and transcription. P1 from Negros Occidental is the chief editor of a multimedia news platform and has been working as a journalist for more than 25 years. P2 is affiliated with a local news outlet in Capiz and has worked as a local journalist for over 10 years. P3 is an editor of a government radio station in Iloilo and has been in the industry for over 39 years. P4 is working in Negros Occidental and is now the editor-in-chief of a multimedia news platform and has been a journalist for more than 18 years. P5 works in Guimaras and has been writing news for over 20 years. P6 is from Aklan and is affiliated with a national news media organization but has been stationed as a local journalist for more than 11 years. P7 is a journalist from Antique with more than 21 years of experience writing local news. P8 is a seasoned journalist from Negros Occidental with 25 years of experience writing news for national and local media organizations. Lastly, P9 is from Iloilo and has been a journalist for more than 34 years.

Table 1 *Profile of the Filipino Journalists in Western Visayas*

Alias	Years in Service	Location	Sex
P 1	25 Years	Negros Occidental	Male
P 2	10 Years	Capiz	Female
P 3	39 Years	Iloilo	Female
P 4	18 Years	Negros Occidental	Male
P 5	20 Years	Guimaras	Male
P 6	11 Years	Aklan	Female
P 7	21 Years	Antique	Female
P 8	25 Years	Negros Occidental	Female
P 9	34 Years	Iloilo	Female

This study is clustered into four major segments: (1) journalistic practices in the new media, (2) practices that implicate objectivity in news writing, (3) assessment of the hierarchy of influence model in the news writing process, and (4) news writing framework.

Journalistic Practices in the New Media

This study came up with six themes describing the practices of Filipino journalists in the new media: (1) Understanding the "SAS" (Short Attention Span) Audience, (2) Digital News Gathering, (3) Fact-finders, (4) Multimedia Journalists, (5) Digital Media Editors, and (6) Safeguarding in the New Media (Table 2).

Table 2 *Journalistic Practices in the New Media*

SN	Themes (Labels)	Sub-themes
1	Understanding the "SAS" (Short Attention Span) Audience	Audience Behavior in the new media
2	Digital News Gathering	Newsgathering using technology News content in the digital age Investigative process today
3	Fact-finders	Fact-checking in the new media landscape
4	Multimedia Journalists	Writing Style in new media Dealing with cybercrimes and cyber libel
5	Digital Media Editors	Editor's role in the new media landscape
6	Safeguarding in the New Media	Accountability in new media Correcting errors in the digital age

Understanding the "SAS" (Short Attention Span) Audience

The ***audience's behavior*** towards journalism changed due to the advent of new media, affecting Filipino journalists' practices. The audience today is busy with their daily lives and preoccupied with all the happenings in the world. Most of the local audience in Western Visayas are busy juggling work and maintaining balance in their personal life. However, no matter how busy the locals are, they still find it necessary to read the news and stay updated with the current events happening around their area, country, and even globally. The general public still seems hungry for information and wants to remain relevant to make informed decisions for their lives, the community, and society. News about highly influential people or stories about random folks is interesting for the local audience, especially if it will affect their day-to-day activities. The local audience is also interested in local news, regional events, festivities, and business developments since they are smaller communities in the province.

With the advent of social media and digital technologies, the digital audience now has a short attention span (SAS), especially in consuming news. With the birth of different social media networking sites providing entertainment through short video clips, random memes, and even online shopping, it lessens the time for the digital audience to stay and read news online. The digital audience's attention can be taken away instantly by witty posts, intriguing videos, and captivating headlines. The explosion of digital content available in social media created the generation of the "SAS" audience. These new breeds of SAS audiences require news creators to package and deliver stories in a quick, direct, and fast-paced nature. News writers need to compete with various forms of digital content to get the attention of the digital audience with limited and short attention spans.

Moreover, with the development of digital technology, the digital audience spends more time connected on social media while interacting with their families and friends. While connected in the social community, the digital audience also updates themselves with various news and current affairs. They utilize their time to multitask to stay updated with news and current affairs while socializing with their networks.

Knowing that the SAS audience has a limited attention span and journalists have competition in social media in terms of digital content, they should know how to be brief, concise, and direct to the point in writing news stories.

P4 narrated, "It's not anymore what I like, but what the public like. It will not work if I write only the information I want to give them. I have to give the people the information they like and need. So it's imperative that you study your market and you understand your audience."

It is essential for journalists to genuinely understand the digital (SAS) audience so they can perform their job better. Understanding audience behavior affects the news coverage and placement of stories (Nelson & Lei, 2018). Understanding the needs and demands of the SAS audience is necessary so they can fit, readjust, and tailor their journalistic practices and continue doing their work in serving the public. These changes in the qualities of the digital (SAS) audience would entail the journalists to change their writing styles, offer different dynamics in news writing, and consider other perspectives in news production. Multimedia journalists must realize these changes to address the needs and want of the public they serve.

A media environment that prioritizes audience attributes would certainly undergo significant adjustments to their journalistic practices (Hamilton, 2016). Considering the developments in the characteristics of news consumers, the

journalistic practices of news production should also evolve to fit the digital audience's behavior. It is necessary that multimedia journalists truly understand the SAS audience by giving the news content they like to consume and packaging the story that would meet their short attention span. This would entail news stories written with few words, including only the most relevant and essential details.

P8 highlighted, "We have a very young, restless, distracted, and uninformed audience. So we have to learn and understand what people like. That's why nowadays, no one writes too long essays anymore. So why will I argue with that? It's what the audience like. In short, I must consider my audience and change my journalistic practice to suit their needs and demands.

Digital News Gathering

The participants described their new practices in finding news in the digital age with three subthemes which are (1) news gathering using technology, (2) finding newsworthy stories in the digital age, and (3) doing the investigative process in the digital age.

The introduction of digital **news gathering can be attributed to the development of technology** and its advantage in the investigation process and verification of facts and information. One of the benefits of technology for journalists is making news gathering more manageable and convenient in this digital age.

Through digital technology like the internet and social media, multimedia journalists can monitor news on social media, other media outlets, and even national and international news. Multimedia journalists must be updated with all the relevant activities around their area. They cannot be left behind in updating the digital (SAS) audience about issues concerning their life and society. Aside from this, the

information posted online needs to be highlighted and followed up and may even require more in-depth contextualization.

There are instances when other media outlets will get exclusive news, so it's also vital that local journalists will keep tabs on their competitors. And monitoring the news contents of their competitors is made accessible because of the advent of social media and access to the internet.

Multimedia journalists can also monitor reports posted by national and international news agencies because this may also implicate the lives of the local people. Any relevant and important information may be given local flavors and context highlighting how it would affect the lives of the local readers. Since digital technology made connecting with people from different parts of the world possible, we must realize how interconnected society is. Any international conflicts happening on the other side of the world may significantly affect the country and the region's locality. Staying connected through digital devices and technologies allowed multimedia journalists to stay updated with current affairs worldwide.

P8 shared, "In the newsroom, we also monitor our competitors, national news, international news, and even online news. Because you cannot be left behind, you have to stay updated with what's happening around".

Aside from this, journalists can now contact their sources much faster, easier, and cheaper because of mobile phones and social media. Through technology, multimedia journalists can reach their sources quickly and more efficiently. With the availability of the internet, multimedia journalists can use their mobile devices to call their sources to verify facts and information. Journalists do not need to walk for hours or travel the distance to ask questions in the field because they can contact people using technology, especially if the incident is in a far-flung area. Multimedia

journalists can also contact multiple sources, even if they are located in different cities or regions, by using mobile phones or social media. This technological advancement makes digital news gathering faster and quicker because it saves time traveling to the actual location to get bits of information. It made it easier to confirm facts and create stories even from a distance because of digital technology. Aside from this, it's also an efficient cost-saving aspect for multimedia journalists because it will save them transportation expenses to confirm small details of the news story.

P1 shared, "It's actually better now because of technology! Mas damo kame gadgets to use which make the work lighter. Hindi na budlay magcontact sa mga tawo! Our sources became more accessible. Sa ngayon, hindi na kinanglan maglakad ng pila ka-oras or magsaka sa bukid, kay macontact mo na imo source thru cellphone. In short, news gathering became faster and easier. But still, you have to collect information personally and verify facts like the traditional way. (It's actually better now because of technology. We have more gadgets to use which make the work lighter. It's now easier to contact different people. Our sources became more accessible. Nowadays, we do not need to walk or go to far-flung areas because we can call our sources through our cell phones.)

Another thing is journalists can now use their mobile phones to capture good-quality photos and video recordings using smartphones and the latest gadgets. Contemporary journalists do not need to carry heavy equipment all the time because they now have good-quality devices that are lightweight and can also be used for digital newsgathering. Multimedia journalists now carry smartphones that can be utilized as a voice recorder, a high-definition camera, and a video recorder. With the increasing demand for digital technology, new products are being produced daily that can be useful for multimedia journalists. Digital audiences are also proven to be

more graphically and visually oriented. Thus, every multimedia journalist must have a reliable, high-quality smartphone or gadget. The digital audience is now looking for exciting photos and engaging videos that will capture their attention, making them glued to their social media and consume news stories.

Multimedia journalists can also use their laptops anytime and anywhere to write news stories to finish them on time. They are no longer confined to a newsroom workspace because they can work and complete their stories anywhere, even in the field. Laptops and digital devices also allowed for more straightforward checking of spelling errors and minor grammar lapses. These practical innovations are making multimedia journalists' work more convenient. Moreover, multimedia journalists can email their news stories to their editors online.

Additionally, multimedia journalists can maximize their time working on their news stories using their laptops while looking for new leads on the field. Communication and correspondence between journalists and editors are now maintained for easier reference because of the Internet and email. This is all made possible because of digital technology paving digital newsgathering.

Finally, the internet is a massive advantage for journalists because research is made easier and accessible at the fingertips of multimedia journalists anytime and anywhere using digital devices and gadgets. Multimedia journalists can now easily cross-check information using the internet. They can even do internet research for information they aren't knowledgeable of. Researching unfamiliar terms and information is a must for multimedia journalists so they will be prepared to discuss things when they write their news stories. Moreover, resources such as public documents can now be easily downloaded online. This made the work of multimedia journalists easier because it removed the hassle of personally securing documents

to different offices. Accessing documents online is more efficient and convenient for multimedia journalists, made possible through digital technology and the internet.

P9 highlighted, "Before, you really have to go out and get documents on different locations, but now, you can easily download press releases, official documents from the government, and other related documents online."

Technology supplements the enhancement of the relationship of multimedia journalists with other social institutions resulting in changes in their journalistic practices. Mobile devices with internet connectivity, camera, and messaging capabilities served as the precursors of a rise in the use of technology for news production (Westlund, 2013). These technological innovations pushed traditional journalists to use mobile devices in news reporting. Moreover, the widespread use of mobile devices has allowed journalists to complete various activities whenever and wherever they choose by using digital technology. The advent of technology positively influences the news-gathering process, making journalists' life easier and more manageable. Moreover, it's easier for multimedia journalists to transact with other organizations and collaborate with multiple institutions through digital technology.

Multimedia journalists have multiple concepts of identifying newsworthy content in the digital age. Recognizing a situation's newsworthiness or an issue is the first practice a journalist should develop (Ladera & Lebrilla, 2012). In digital news gathering, the most common type of news content the journalists pursue is "human interest." As long as the people are involved, and the story significantly impacts the lives of the people and society, these are considered newsworthy for the digital audience.

Multimedia journalists' fundamental concern is to look for news stories involving people and how these stories would implicate the lives of the local readers. Although, Popioco (2010) highlights that Filipino journalists in Western Visayas often have their outlook on what stories are newsworthy. Human interest is still considered the fundamental element of newsworthy content, even in digital news writing. Multimedia journalists need to find relevant events or happenings about prominent or ordinary people that will immensely impact the daily routines and activities of the local readers. Local readers are always concerned about their life and how random news could affect their daily routines. The digital audience is always on alert for what the news can bring or implicate to their busy lives, asking what they can get or what the report can do to them. Random happenings may include minor incidents to a more extensive and complicated story about the interconnectedness of social dimensions of our perceived reality.

P2 said, "If we go to the basic journalistic principle, there's a saying - you have to give the people what they need to know, but you also have to give them what they should know." P 2 added, "It should concern everyone from politics, developmental issues, insurgencies, and local contexts like local and economic concerns—for example, local sugar industry crimes and peace and order."

Nowadays, ordinary people can become celebrities using social media. In social media, ordinary people produce content about their everyday life activities, which are sometimes highlighted and become newsworthy. Multimedia journalists monitor such activities because it still has the fundamental element of human interest and may potentially develop as newsworthy content. Video clips of ordinary people affected by a particular scenario or daily encounters with random local officers may result in a more significant situation that can become interesting for digital readers.

Any news stories or activities that may seem small may yield a more extensive news outbreak once the multimedia journalists investigate and give local context.

P3 explained, “Any news about people could become good stories. You know, mga tao ngayon, feeling nila at sa isip nila they are celebrities. (Nowadays, everyone thinks and feels that they are celebrities.)”

Filipino journalists in Western Visayas are focused on stories about the people and the implication of a situation to their lives. Mellado and Van Dalen (2013) articulated that journalists write stories questioning political figures and personalities, holding them accountable for their actions, especially if it concerns the people. It can then be stated that multimedia journalists have their perspectives on what human interest is. The topics and stories dictating human interests highly depend on the journalists' values and beliefs. But the most crucial consideration is the news stories should be about people and how this can help or implicate their lives and the community.

P5 said, “Unang una, is it useful for the people? (Primary consideration is will be useful for the people?) Journalists should select stories that benefit people and give them the information they need and want.”

Another common type of news content for multimedia journalists in Western Visayas is providing updates on regional events and local activities. The digital audience wants to be updated with the current events and activities happening in the region that directly impact their day-to-day activities. Ladera and Lebrilla's (2012) mentioned that relevance, significance, timeliness, and public interest are the common factors for Filipino journalists in Iloilo City in selecting news stories.

Local readers are drawn to the regional festivities and events because they are smaller communities and hold culture closer to their hearts since they are from a

closely knitted and conservative province. The various regional events and activities have direct implications, especially for the lives of ordinary people. These happenings attract thousands of visitors to the area resulting in an influx of jobs, an economic jump, and even a rise in local migration. Major activities and events concern the digital audience, making them interested in online news. Through digital technology and social media, regional activities and events can easily be shared online, resulting in exponential reach and public dissemination.

Finally, other events may also include national or global happenings that may affect the day-to-day activities of the local people. Multimedia journalists provide contextualized stories trimming down facts and information to suit the local audience. Multimedia journalists present national or global events to local readers so they will be updated with what's happening around the country and even the world. Locals in Western Visayas care about what's happening in the region, the country, and even the world today.

P1 shared an example, “we monitor the price of the onion ever since nag shoot-up ang iya price. We monitor ano na mga gatabo sa paligid and we write stories about it. (We monitor the price of onions ever since its price shoot up. We monitor what is happening in the area and we write stories about it.) We keep the people updated about the price hike and how the people are responding to the price hike.”

Bode (2016) said daily news on current events is increasingly incorporated into various activities, websites, and genres. Although what journalists do to make their content more unique remains uncertain, offering multiple topics and subjects to appeal to the digital audience is necessary (Nielsen, 2015). Regional events and happenings are also significant for journalists to follow. Events and occurrences

concerning various social institutions considerably influence the stories multimedia journalists pursue and write.

P7 said, “may ara man people who really want to be updated with local policies, business, traffic reports, accidents, etc. (There are people who really want to be updated with local policies, business, traffic reports, accidents, etc.) These stories also pick up because it concerns their day-to-day activities.”

Lastly, in digital news gathering, a real multimedia journalist values the importance of personally going into the field and doing the **investigative process** themselves. It is still crucial for multimedia journalists to collect information, ask the people around them, get all sides of the story, and understand the situation. Journalists should still be diligent in doing the arduous tasks of data gathering, even in the digital age, to get all the facts and complete the necessary information before they can start writing their news stories. These would entail the multimedia journalists to investigate extensively and use digital technology to get to the bottom of the story. Although digital technology may ease some work for multimedia journalists, it is still necessary for them to go into the field and expose themselves to the action field.

P2 emphasized “that diligence will win in the end because this will make your story stand out. Makita in your news story, the level of skills and diligence you put in news gathering and verifying information. (Diligence will win in the end because this will make your story stand out. The level of skills and diligence you put in news gathering and verifying information will show in your news story.).”

With the advent of digital technology, journalists should hone their skills in investigative work to take their work to the next level. Journalists need to practice traditional data-driven news gathering and show critical analysis of events and

situations. It entails going beyond the basics of news writing and dwelling extensively to uncover more profound stories. Technology should not be used as a substitute for investigative journalists (Pavlik, 2000) but as a supplement to improve the outputs of multimedia journalists.

On-site multimedia journalists can make observations, raise critical questions, and conduct interviews which are essential in digital newsgathering. Multimedia journalists should continually probe their sources or people involved to squeeze information relevant to their news stories. They should practice their keen sense of observation and follow their instincts while doing the arduous task of investigating leads and content. Multimedia journalists do not rely on press releases or a single source but instead do proper investigations and undergo the tedious tasks of finding the truth for the local readers.

P8 narrated, “You are not a real journalist if you don’t go out there, talk to people, and cover the news. We risk our lives to cover the story, umaakyat ako ng bundok, nasusugatan ako, nagsusunog ako ng kilay just to have my full story. (We risk our lives just to cover a story! I climb mountains, got bruises, and worked overtime just to have my full story.)” P 8 further stated, “iba talaga when you ask questions because you’ll know the whole story and how you’ll write your news story. (It’s different when you ask the question because you’ll know the whole story and how you’ll write the news story.)”

Fact-finders

This study highlights the importance of verification today, especially with the advent of social media. Journalists should do **fact-checking even in the new media landscape** by going personally out in the field. Whether they are traditional or

contemporary journalists, the vetting process is deemed vital in the digital newsroom. Salvosa and Esguerra (2021) said Filipino journalists found it imperative to check facts in the field and validate the information from multiple sources. Multimedia journalists understand their role as advocates of finding the truth and getting to the bottom of the story by collecting all valuable facts and information. Multimedia journalists must practice their duty of digging up details and finding the truth even at the expense of their safety. Finding facts should also not be one-sided; that is why multimedia journalists fact-check every tiny detail, getting all sides of the story. Multimedia journalists do not work on writing their news stories with unverified information or not getting all sides of the story.

P1 said, “hindi ako naga-rely only on press releases. For example, may ara accident reports, makadto ko sa hospital and ask the victims what really happened. I ask them if ok ba sila? Are they all safe? Hindi ako basta lang magpati sa kung ano mga ginahambal ng pulis. (I do not rely only on press releases. For example, if there's an accident, I'll go to the hospital and ask the victims what happened and whether they are all safe. I do not just believe what the police are saying.)”

Moreover, multimedia journalists do not rely only on press releases or tips, especially from their social media inboxes. It is essential to understand that multimedia journalists are not just transcribers or translators of information from sources to the digital audience. Multimedia journalists process the information they get from possible sources and still do the fact-checking and vetting process. Vetting is necessary for journalism as it entails multimedia journalists doing background checks and examining the information. Multimedia journalists do not just copy and retype press releases and make their news stories. They should critically analyze the

data from press releases, contextualize stories, and present the news to highlight how the situation may implicate the local readers.

Another thing, with the accessibility of the internet, it paved the way for ordinary people to contact news outlets through their social media accounts quickly. Such easy access to news media organizations allowed media illiterate and disinformation peddlers to enter the journalism world. This is why multimedia journalists should screen all information they get from their sources, especially from their social media accounts. Multimedia journalists should scrutinize the info and check the veracity of the facts. The first thing multimedia journalists should check is the credibility of the origin of the source. If the account proves legit, multimedia journalists can contact them to shed more light on the story. However, suppose the source comes from an unverified account and does not have contact details; there's a big possibility that the source is only scheming and hopes that multimedia journalists will fall into their trap of spreading lies and fake news. With this, multimedia journalists should be prudent in verifying information from reliable and credible sources before writing their news stories.

P2 narrated, "You know, in our social media, we received many messages, photos, and videos. So when we think the story is interesting, we call the sender and ask where they got the photos. May ara incident, na ang sender sends photo na hindi man sa kanila. They got it from the Internet, and they send it to us. (There are instances when the sender sends photos they do not own. They got it from the internet and sent it to us.) So as journalists, we should really verify and double-check information before we start writing our news stories."

Multimedia journalists should also not rely on only one source but must have multiple sources of information to verify and cross-check the information they

gathered. Additionally, Ladera and Lebrilla (2012) said that the media industry is built on trust, more specifically by Filipino journalists in Iloilo City. They should gather facts not only from one source but needs to be verified with two or more credible sources. This process could ensure that the information is not biased and comes from all sides of the story giving more depth to the news and providing verified facts and details from the people involved. It is crucial that all angles will be covered and all possible people can give their statements to make the story complete and ready for public consumption. The digital audience seems skeptical of incomplete news, unverified facts, and bias to one side of news writing.

Moreover, multimedia journalists must only get credible sources relevant to the story they are pursuing to make their news stories solid. It is important that they could find ways to be connected directly to the people involved or at least to the people closely linked to the story. Multimedia journalists do not just interview random people not connected to the story because this will diminish the credibility of their news story. This is why multimedia journalists should build their rapport and credibility to expand their network, increasing their connections to different people. Multimedia journalists know they should be friends with the lowest-ranking people to the most influential personalities because they will eventually need their contacts once a story comes up.

Multimedia Journalists

In writing news in the new media, multimedia journalists shared the following practices, which are (1) writing styles in the new media, (2) dealing with cybercrimes and cyber libel, and (3) editing news using technology.

Various and multiple practices of **writing styles in the new media** were observed. First, multimedia journalists ensure that they use simple language and that ordinary people can understand their news stories. Multimedia journalists ensure that local readers can understand their vocabulary and terminologies. They should learn how to suit their language that would cater to the liking of their news consumers. Local readers in the regions also have multiple dialects, so some news is contextualized using their own dialect. However, most multimedia journalists write in English to cater to the digital audience. Multimedia journalists must present their news stories to most local people. News stories should also be presented in a simple and understandable sentence structure that the digital audience can easily understand.

Moreover, highly technical terms and verbose language are discouraged because they cater to only a few selected target audiences. Local audiences in Western Visayas also have residents who belong to minority and ethnic groups. Thus, multimedia journalists' language must be simple, direct to the point, and comprehensible.

The digital (SAS) audiences are very selective and picky in reading news stories due to their busy schedules, short attention span, and personal preferences. Journalists should learn to adapt to the digital audience and cater to their liking. Society, as the critical social player, should be prioritized since they are the ones who will be consuming the news content. The digital audience demands that news writers be more descriptive in presenting news stories. Because of their short attention span, the digital audience must feel attracted and engrossed in the story to make them glued to their gadgets and finish the news story. Multimedia journalists should provide implicit details to capture the attention of the SAS audience. They

should be able to present interesting facts using captivating photos or videos and catch the digital audience's attention. Most importantly, the SAS audience should feel they are in the actual scenario when reading the news stories. This becomes the most challenging practice for journalists - to be more descriptive in presenting news content considering that the digital audience is selective and more critical in consuming news stories.

Additionally, multimedia journalists should maintain a conversational tone in their news stories. The digital audience must feel relaxed and comfortable while reading the news content. Multimedia journalists should maintain neutrality in presenting their news content. The digital audience should not feel stressed or angry while reading the news, or other digital content will steal their attention. It is also imperative that multimedia journalists are not so aggressive and authoritarian in expressing their voices reflected in their news content. This may seem off for the digital audience, and take it against the multimedia journalists. Multimedia journalists should remain composed and calm in presenting news stories to make them conversational for the digital audience and public consumption. This is especially true when news stories are heavy and might have a significant implication on the lives of local readers. Multimedia journalists must present serious information that will not shock the digital audience and create panic in the public.

P4 mentioned, "You have to write and deal with all the senses – sight, hearing, smell, and taste. Basically, you need to describe the news explicitly to your audience. Dapat mafeel at isipin ng audience that they are actually there with you. (Your audience should feel and think they are there with you.) Another thing, your news story must be simple and conversational."

Additionally, contemporary journalists should now be brief and concise in reporting news stories. The digital (SAS) audience does not like lengthy news articles because they get quickly bored and distracted by too much information. With the competition of digital content rampant in social media, multimedia journalists should practice reporting news stories as short as possible with minimum words but with all the relevant and factual information. News stories should be direct to the point in telling the readers the gist of the contents and what's in it for them. SAS audience doesn't need background information but only looks for the most relevant information that may implicate their day-to-day activities. The SAS audience can do the fact-checking and reading of other related articles should they need to read more about the news. Journalists should adjust their practices in delivering their news to capture their audience's interest and refrain from giving too much information but only the relevant ones.

P7 narrated, "You have to rethink and also update your style in writing. In social media, you cannot write long stories. You have to be brief and concise. Short but with complete information."

Kaneshige (2014) emphasized that journalists should be clear, compelling, and concise. Writing news stories does not follow a standard template. Still, it should be written in an assertive tone, captivating the interest of the digital audience by telling them to value factual information.

P8 shared, "Usually 2-3 sentences will do and post a compelling photo with a 5-second video. That's it! Because this is what the audience wants nowadays!"

Interestingly, the digital (SAS) audience is now content with photos, short video clips, and minimal news descriptions. The digital audience wants captivating images or short video clips alongside the news story. Quality photos and videos in

news stories are necessary because the digital audience is now more visually oriented. Multimedia journalists should find good pictures or video clips that can catch the attention and interest of the public. This is why multimedia journalists must secure good-quality photos or interesting short video clips for their news content. Digital media editors require multimedia journalists for these materials to increase the chances of being selected for publication. News materials without photos or videos may sometimes get axed in the news production, no matter how relevant or vital the implications may be to the lives of the local readers.

This new development in news writing also emphasized the need for multimedia journalists to hone their skills in photojournalism. Honing their photojournalism skills may require multimedia journalists to tell a news story even with their photos alone without a lengthy discussion of the details. Photojournalism could captivate the digital audience's attention and may hook them to consume and finish their news stories. Photojournalism requires attention to detail, creativity, and talent in building a story without using words. This change in the journalistic practice immensely revolutionizes news packaging in today's world of journalism.

Additionally, multimedia journalists should have skills in capturing video materials that can suffice even without lengthy discussions of the news story. The video should be brief but contain sufficient information to give the digital audience enough information about the story's context. Multimedia journalists must upgrade their skills to use digital technology, especially in video recording. Moreover, multimedia journalists should be familiar with cybercrimes, especially when using technology to get photos and video recordings. There are legal considerations that multimedia journalists should be aware of, especially in the digital age.

Hernandez and Rue (2015) mentioned the term “news package,” which consists of multifaceted stories through an organized layout, such as a video paired with text or an interactive graphic. With digital technologies, journalists learned to present their stories with videos, photos, graphics, and others. Photos may add new dimensions of meaning to a text (Hall, 2019). Mitchell (2013) articulates that digital journalism combines mixed media, creating varying degrees of interpretation and interaction. However, how journalists have effectively used new media in digital journalism varies over time (Jacobson et al., 2016). The advancement of technology implicating the world of news writing opened spaces for different news writing and reporting platforms.

P1 narrated, “with the use of technology, makakakuha ka na ng good quality photos and videos na pede mo magamit sa imo news story. (With technology, you can have good-quality pictures and videos for your news story.) This is important nowadays because this is what people seek.”

P4 shared, “In the digital platform, we cannot proceed without good videos even if you have a good write-up, it will not work. If you have a good write-up but you don’t have a video, you will be put in the least priority of news stories. But good story plus good video, then automatically, you will be on number 1 priority.”

Aside from the basics, the digital audience wants to see a different angle and context of the story. Seasoned journalists do not just settle for the basic information but look for a different perspective and bring something new to the audience. By doing so, multimedia journalists are giving something new to the reader that makes their news story more exciting and captivating. They provide a richer context to the report by highlighting possible implications for the lives of ordinary people.

Multimedia journalists should present stories to make the local readers realize how

their stories affect their day-to-day living and activities. Multimedia journalists challenge themselves to dig deeper into the account and provide a fresh angle to set them apart from other journalists. They practice their journalistic instinct in providing richer contextualization so the local readers can relate to the story.

Different angles and fresh perspectives may also include accomplishments and good deeds of influential personalities and even ordinary people. Such news contents are also viable for the digital audience. The digital audience is also keen to read positive news around the region. Such news contents provide valid reasons pushing the digital audience to be interested in the news stories and consume their news content. Giving hope to the people and providing them with options to contemplate is also considered newsworthy content. News stories must tickle the digital audience's minds, encouraging them to act and be critical of their next action plan. News stories provide avenues for the digital audience to analyze their options towards making an informed decision affecting their life, the community, and the society they live in.

P1 said, "If the news is bad or something like a tragedy, I try to find an angle where I can show the people's hope. It's also important to show their ambitions and accomplishments. You find an angle that can showcase the extent of damage it will cost to the people, not just focus on the basic information about the tragedy. This will make your news story more relatable to the audience."

P2 narrated, "Journalists provide intelligent context to the news with a sane voice. Dapat makahatag ka rason sa mga tawo to read your news. (You should give reasons to the people to read your news stories)."

Consequently, digital news writing is more complicated because of **cybercrimes and cyber libel**. Multimedia journalists must learn to protect

themselves from copyright issues, which may lead to cybercrimes. The rise of digital technology paves the way for the rapid explosion of digital crimes. Multimedia journalists should practice extreme caution in dealing with online issues that may lead to cybercrimes. One of these is the legal issue of taking photos or videos of people without their permission, especially if this will be posted online. With the massive reach of social media, journalists must get permission from people before publishing their news stories to avoid repercussions in their practice.

Moreover, the photos and video clips received online must also have permission from the direct owner. There are instances when the public grabs materials online and send them to the local news outlet's social media accounts. Multimedia journalists should know that they must first verify the material's authenticity and trace its ownership. They cannot just post photos or videos without securing the appropriate permission to use the materials. This negligence could lead to cybercrimes and legal implications for multimedia journalists.

P4 narrated, "In digital, we have copyright cases. You cannot take a photo of somebody else without asking their permission."

Another consideration is cyber libel. Journalists should be cautious in writing their news stories, especially in the digital age where everyone and everything is already accessible online. Cyber libel is a huge mess and a dreadful scenario for multimedia journalists, especially if ethics is taken for granted. Small details may lead to the complexity of fighting against cyber libel when taken out of context. That is why multimedia journalists should be conscientious in writing their news stories. Multimedia journalists should fact-check and validate all the information in their news stories to ensure they won't face cyber libel attacks from those involved in the news. All correspondence, interviews, and evidence records should be kept just in case of

unforeseen incidents. This will also protect multimedia journalists from cyber libel attacks.

Journalists should take care of themselves, especially with the threat of various agencies killing democracy in the country. In the Philippines, the government is attacking journalists by undermining their credibility in the eyes of the general public (Herr, 2020). It is simple for government officials to add propaganda and attack the newsroom organization. Puente (2020) highlighted that although there is every reason for journalists to be careful, efforts to suppress the media won't ever cause the sector to cease serving a social purpose.

Additionally, Sinpeng and Koh (2022) mentioned that Asia is an incredibly hostile environment for journalism online. But despite the high likelihood of state repression, news organizations in Southeast Asia (including the Philippines) continue to cover and look into politically and socially sensitive issues. Multimedia journalists in the Philippines still have a strong passion for fighting for our democracy and the freedom of the press. The torch of journalism is still ablaze for Filipino multimedia journalists who are choosing to fight against oppression and efforts to silence the media. Efforts from various journalism groups across the country are intact for their cause to defend democracy and stay faithful to their calling of serving the Filipino people by providing facts and relevant information necessary for the country's development.

P9 said, "There is a cybercrime and cyber libel. Journalists have to take care of themselves because of the changes in the laws due to social media and the world wide web."

Another new innovative practice for multimedia journalists is the capability to **edit their news stories using technology**. Multimedia journalists can now edit

news stories using mobile phones anytime and anywhere. Digital technology and mobile devices allowed multimedia journalists to correct typographical errors while connected to the internet instantly. There's also the ease of using artificial intelligence like auto-correct in spelling to minimize simple mistakes in the news story. Multimedia journalists can also work and edit their news content any time of the day using their mobile devices. These digital innovations made it more convenient for multimedia journalists to react to errors, especially if it's only a minor mistake. Multimedia journalists edit news stories faster and more efficiently using online applications and laptops. Online applications and language editors help multimedia journalists polish their news stories making their work look more professional.

P1 narrated, "We now have technology helping us in editing. It's easier to correct spelling mistakes or grammar errors because of computers. Now we are also using applications that make our work easier and look more professional than before."

Aside from this, mobile devices allow multimedia journalists to publish their news stories anytime and anywhere just by being connected to the internet. They are not bounded to work only in the confined spaces of the digital newsroom. Digital technology offers flexible working areas in the digital space for multimedia journalists to work on their news stories. With a simple click, multimedia journalists can easily publish news stories online.

P8 reiterated, "There is no problem with mobile journalism because we use our mobile phones and technology to post and edit our news stories."

Laptops and digital devices now also offer features such as word count, making the work of multimedia journalists much faster. They can also play around

with their words using their laptops and gadgets. Available applications such as synonyms can make the work of multimedia journalists more unconventional and impressive. It is easy for multimedia journalists to copy and paste their articles using their laptops, making their job easier. This is only possible if multimedia journalists are well-versed in digital technology and have the skills to utilize available application tools offered by digital technology.

P9 shared, "It's more of technicality, now everything is easier with technology. You can copy-paste, edit your story online using your mobile phone, and even utilize word count."

Digital Media Editors

The **editors play a significant role in selecting news** in the new media landscape. Digital media editors screen, check and even verify the news story of the multimedia journalists in the new media landscape. First and foremost, the digital media editor must find the news story relevant and significant to cater to the needs and demands of the digital audience. Before a news story can reach local readers, it must first pass the eagle eyes of the digital media editors scrutinizing its news content. Multimedia journalists thus need to consider first the preference of the digital media editors because they decide on what news to publish. Digital media editors ensure that only newsworthy content is published for news production. Suppose they find the news story irrelevant to the local readers and has minimal impact on society. In that case, this may be returned to the multimedia journalists for better contextualization or reframing of the story.

P4 narrated, “We gather everything and collect all the stories that we have. As the editor-in-chief, I rank the news stories according to the most important ones. So I get to decide which stories can make it to the top 10 most important stories.”

Digital media editors also check the completeness of the story, the context of the article, and whether it has a good-quality photo or short video clips accompanying the news story. There are instances when the digital news editor also checks the validity of the information in the news articles with their sources on the ground. They can easily fact-check the validity of the information by using their mobile phones to verify the details with their sources.

And if the news story has missing elements, the digital media editor sorts it out with multimedia journalists. The digital media editor may request additional information to substantiate the news story further. They can also comment and suggest ways to better contextualize the news story more suitable for the local readers. Digital media editors can also see if the news story is biased or leaning towards one party. In this case, the digital media editor mentors the multimedia journalists to improve their practice better and more professionally.

Safeguarding in the New Media

In dealing with errors, journalists honor **accountability** much more **in the new media**. It is essential that multimedia journalists are being held accountable for their actions and news stories. Multimedia journalists understand the implication of not taking responsibility for their news stories. The rise of new media made it easier for the public to participate in news production and public discourse. With this, journalists are held accountable by media organizations and the public (Eberwein et

al., 2019). It is easy to put blames and dishonor the credibility of multimedia journalists with the advent of social media.

The media accountability process reiterates that offline and online news consumption can affect journalistic practices in all phases of news production (Domingo & Heikkilä, 2012). Multimedia journalists must remain vigilant in safeguarding their professionalism and journalistic principles by owning up to their mistakes and taking responsibility for their errors. Furthermore, Knobel (2018) argues that there's a more powerful call for better accountability journalism resulting from the proliferation of new media in today's digital media landscape.

P3 shared, "If we committed errors, journalists should be accountable for that. We have to correct our mistakes."

However, local media organizations today do not have clear policies and guidelines for their multimedia journalists to deal with errors and be held accountable for mistakes in their news stories. This norm has an immense implication in maintaining the credibility of the news media organization and multimedia journalists. Without rules and regulations, multimedia journalists may be tempted to continue committing errors since they are not being reprimanded. This practice is evident in Western Visaya's news organization which is a major setback compared to national news organizations. The national news organization is stringent in monitoring the efficiency and accuracy of their journalists and ensures corrective actions and measures will be followed when their journalists commit mistakes. They have policies that outline the course of action when dealing with errors and ensure their journalists are accountable for their actions.

Sadly though, some media outlets in Western Visayas do not mind spelling and grammar errors and are not trying to correct their articles. However, multimedia

journalists should have clear actions to rectify mistakes and be responsible for their published news stories. They also owe it to the public to ensure that all information is accurate, factual, and error-free since the public sees multimedia journalists as persons in authority. Minor errors and mistakes diminish the multimedia journalists' power, especially for critical readers who can spot-on identify inconsistency and inaccurate details.

P7 articulated, "News organizations should have their policies when dealing with these kinds of things like errors, corrections, fact-checking, etc. The news organization should be transparent, so the people can understand what really happened."

Local news media organizations should also clearly explain to their readers what happened and why the error was committed and show the public that they are ensuring that their multimedia journalists are held accountable for their news stories. This is especially true when the errors are not just superficial or spelling errors like inaccurate information or developing stories. It cannot be avoided that some multimedia journalists will secure erroneous information from the ground, especially if it's a developing story. This is why it's imperative to be critical in fact-checking the information before writing and publishing the report. Sadly, some local media organizations are not responsible enough to own up to their mistakes. Some local news outlets take down their news stories without explaining what happened and correcting their errors. This practice implicates the credibility of the journalists and the news media organization. The digital audience is critical in consuming news information, so they react more adversely when journalists have errors in their news content. This practice is also not recommended because the public only needs critical factual details to make an informed decision. It is also proven that when the

public consumes inaccurate information, this may lead to confusion, panic, and anxiety.

P8 shared, “The reality is, not all media organizations are strict when it comes to rules and policies concerning inaccuracies and errors. Some of them just take down their article and then that’s enough. But for me, what if you post something that is unverified and there’s an error with the information. What if you cause panic like stampede, trouble, or panic buying? That is very irresponsible on the part of the media. You cannot simply say, I took it down after 30 minutes, so what? What if in those 30 minutes, you caused public outrage, and there will be casualties or chaos.”

Fortunately, some journalists and local media organizations issue **corrective actions** immediately, using their social media accounts and digital technology. Acting on the errors and correcting them is necessary. Multimedia journalists should be mindful of correcting their mistakes as people see them as people in authority, and they remember their mistakes. Multimedia journalists find it imperative to act on fixing the errors as soon as possible to control the damage of the news story and its implication to the reputation of the journalist and the news media organization. Multimedia journalists do not wait days to act on their mistakes because the digital audience may react instantaneously and cause a huge uproar online, bashing and shaming the journalist with incorrect information. They should know how to act quickly and efficiently so the digital audience will not turn their back on them quickly. Von Krogh (2012) asserts the considerable impact of social media accountability. The digital audience’s reaction is explosive and exponential, which may have a massive blow to the career of multimedia journalists. They do not care about your long-standing career and experience in the media industry. If multimedia journalists make a mistake, their reputations will be tarnished.

P9 argued, "Timeliness is of the essence, you do not wait for 2-3 days just to correct your mistakes."

With new technological tools correcting errors online was made easier and more accessible. Some media outlets add a correction button under each article so the readers can quickly provide a comment or correction on a specific article (Eberwein et al., 2019). However, the public has high expectations, with professional journalists publishing only correct and factual information and having little tolerance for errors (Karlsson et al., 2017). Unfortunately, while digital media also makes it possible to correct mistakes, it also makes errors more common.

P3 narrated, "When faced with errors in my news story, I issue an explanation story. For instance, stating that initially, the police thought that there were 6 deaths, but eventually, they found out that the other 2 have weak pulse but are alive. So I have to update and correct my story."

Local media organizations in Western Visayas issued a corrective news article stating the error and explaining in detail what happened with the news article. The new articles state the previous story and update the local readers with the latest facts and information. Through this action, the journalists and the media organization can clear the misunderstanding. They will keep the digital audience updated and well-informed of what really happened in the news story.

P5 shared, "sa iban na station, they will write a new story and quote the previous story stating the error. (In other stations, they will issue a new story and quote the previous story stating the error)."

Practices that implicate objectivity in news writing

Table 3 narrates the practices in the digital age of news writing that implicate objectivity in the new media. This study came up with five themes describing the changes in the practices of Filipino journalists in Western Visayas. They are (1) the New Media landscape, (2) the Roles of Journalists in the New Media, (3) Local and National News Agencies Today, (4) New Challenges in the New Media, and (5) Malpractices of Journalists Today.

Table 3 *Practices that Implicate Objectivity in News Writing*

SN	Theme (Labels)	Sub-themes
1	New Media Landscape	New media
2	Gatekeeper of Truth and Democracy	Fight disinformation Bigger Responsibility in New Media
3	Local and National News Agencies Today	Differences in Practices Today
4	The New Challenges	Technology and staying relevant Economic situation
5	Corrupt Journalists	Corruption in media

New Media Landscape

The ***new media*** has a massive impact on journalism. Traditional media is slowly dying but continues to thrive primarily because of the emergence of new media. Most media organizations are shifting their focus to digital platforms and increasing their presence on different social media sites. New media includes all communication platforms using digital technology. These include social media, websites, blogs, video and photo-sharing platforms, and even SMS. Because of these changes in the media landscape, journalists should also innovate their practice to adapt to societal trends. News media organizations should invest in digital

platforms because the digital audience spends more time browsing the internet for news and current events.

The study of Masip et al. (2015) highlighted that the digital audience prefers to continue to respect journalism as a profession and the traditional media institutions as the primary producers of news and the most dependable sources of information rather than turning to alternative sources like citizen journalism or non-traditional media or taking the initiative by producing their content.

P9 narrated, “Mainstream media thrives because of social media. Although, I do not look at the changes in today’s media landscape as bad because this is how the world evolves.”

Consequently, the digital audience already shifted their news consumption to new media, which has immense implications for the print industry (Westlund, 2013). Today, local news media organizations do not print their news editions daily but have limited print production due to the proliferation of new media. Most local news outlets publish their news edition only three times a week. They still have to run their printed newspapers to cater to traditional media patrons who prefer to read printed newspapers. However, their digital presence should continue to be visible daily. The news content in both printed and new media is the same. The only difference between the two is the platform where the news is published. Any news story printed in the newspaper should also be published online and vice versa. With this emerging threat (Westlund & Fardigh, 2011) and imminent change to the media landscape (Nel, 2010), it is speculated that printed newspapers might soon be obsolete.

P3 mentioned, “I can say that print media is a dying industry because of the emergence of new media. To illustrate, in our media outlet, pre-pandemic, we are

printing our issues like 6 days a week. But during the pandemic, we have to cease printing. Slowly, we returned now, and we are only printing 3 times a week.”

Gatekeeper of Truth and Democracy

Multimedia journalists now ***have a bigger responsibility*** as the gatekeeper of truth and democracy by providing facts to the community and helping to build society. Their role is to serve the public but with the more considerable responsibility of ensuring that they consume only factual, verified, and confirmed facts and information. The journalists' role extends to providing essential news and information and a better understanding of the situation so the public can make an informed decision.

The primary role of journalists today remains the same: to keep the public updated with what's happening around them and give them the relevant information they need to make informed decisions for their life, the community, and society. Ladera and Lebrilla (2012) stress that journalists' fundamental role is to inform, educate, and entertain. Moreover, Opiniano et al. (2015) said that Philippine news is driven by the same factors of providing the people with the necessary information, educating them about family values, and making them interested in community participation.

P1 said, “The role of the journalists remains the same – to inform, educate, and make people be aware of societal issues. It is very important that people are well-informed and updated about what's happening in their areas.”

P8 added, “Whether you're a traditional or contemporary journalist, the role of journalism remains the same – to inform, persuade, educate, entertain, and motivate the people to act.”

Additionally, the journalists' role is extended to promoting our rich history and culture. It is a fact the Philippines has centuries of exciting stories to tell to this generation. However, the digital audience knows so little about our rich history. Thus, multimedia journalists must ensure that today's generation respects our history and keeps our culture and tradition alive. Multimedia journalists write news stories to keep the region's cultural heritage alive in the hearts and minds of the younger generations. This will also ensure that the digital audience will be knowledgeable of our past and learn from our past experiences.

Most local readers in Western Visayas speak Hiligaynon, which is why some contemporary journalists advocate for promoting this dialect. Some local news organizations translate the news stories into Hiligaynon to cater to the local readers regardless of whether they will be published in print or posted online. The local reporters also use Hiligaynon in their news reporting because this is also acceptable for local news consumers. Some multimedia journalists advocate for using Hiligaynon writing, especially in Western Visayas. This practice could amplify the local dialect's influence and keep the region's culture and tradition. It also proves that some multimedia journalists are biased in using this dialect because of their profound love of their culture and tradition, implicating their objectivity in news writing.

P1 added, "I think journalists should also preserve our culture. They have to keep history alive. I'm also an advocate of Hiligaynon writing."

Multimedia journalists should remain loyal to the people, the truth, and society. Being at the forefront of protecting democracy in the country, multimedia journalists should always fight for the truth and stand guard in protecting the rights of ordinary people. Multimedia journalists are public servants who put the people at the

top of their priorities. They serve as the defender of the helpless and gives hope to the people who are afraid, abused, and neglected. Some multimedia journalists found their calling in helping the poor and marginalized groups making it their bias when writing news stories. They ensured that the people's sufferings were highlighted, especially if rich and influential people were stomping upon their rights. This practice could be evident in how multimedia journalists position their news stories, implicating the news writing process.

P3 shared, "You are in the media because you are in public service. We are fighting for the rights of the people, and this is what we do. I want to be the voice of the people, the voice of the voiceless, and the hope of the hopeless."

P8 emphasized, "Our loyalty is to the truth, and our first obligation is to serve the people."

Fighting disinformation is considered the biggest challenge for multimedia journalists today. This is an essential role for multimedia journalists, especially with the advent of fake news rampant online. Multimedia journalists should advocate their practice in fighting disinformation by blocking peddlers of disinformation, monitoring fake news, and correcting information online so the public can have better decisions affecting their views, opinions, and judgments. If multimedia journalists do not fight disinformation, the digital audience will be ignorant of what's happening in their community. This may implicate the community, and the local readers may suffer because of the information that is not reliable and full of lies. This is why multimedia journalists are very active in social media, debunking news stories that are not factual. They release reports correcting the information so the digital audience will know the truth and disregard the fake news.

P3 shared, “We react to the information online, especially if it’s disinformation that can affect people’s lives. Additionally, we debunk information on social media that are not true.”

The lack of gatekeepers online and the fast-paced nature of the digital media environment provided a platform for the spread of false information (Shin et al., 2018). Balod and Hameleers (2021) argue the rise of disinformation and deception is both a challenge and an opportunity for Philippine journalism to advance as a discipline and practice. Multimedia journalists continue educating local readers on distinguishing fake news from facts. They also inform the digital audience to be conscious of sharing unverified news content because of its implication for society. The challenge remains to keep the digital audience well-informed on identifying fake news and avoid sharing untrusted sources and unverified news stories.

P4 highlighted, “The number one problem dito sa’ten is the spread of disinformation and fake news. And people choose to read fake news rather than credible news stories from real journalists. Confuse na ang mga tao which is fake and real news. (The number one problem is the spread of disinformation and fake news. And people choose to read fake news rather than credible news stories from real journalists. People are now confused with what is fake and real.)”

Local and National News Agencies Today

Meanwhile, the participants have varying perspectives on the difference in the practice of **national and local journalists**. Nowadays, local journalists provide more heart and contextualize the stories to suit the demands of the local audience. Since the local journalists are mainly from the region, they know their history better than the national journalists. Historical background can highlight the value and relevance

of the news content, and local journalists can better provide such trivial matters since they are more familiar with the area and the events that happened in the past.

P1 articulated, “Local journalists provide background to the news story, we do not just generalize and make stories. We know more about our history, so we can provide better contextualization of what really happened.”

Through their experience and personal attachment to the local area, multimedia journalists can provide a deeper side of the story making the news story more enticing for local readers. They can also offer more heart and soul to their news content since they can relate to what’s happening in their locality. Since news content also affects them, they can relate to the story better than national journalists.

P9 narrated, “We are more attached to the story because we have more familiarity with it. That’s why we can give more context and history about the news.”

Local journalists are more attached to the stories and opt to put local flavors to make them more relatable to the local people. The news content must be relatable to the local readers. The local readers must find the value of the news content in their life and the community they live in. They will be hooked to the news story once they see the relevance of the story to their day-to-day activities. Tweaking national and international stories inducing local flavors will make the news content more viable for local readers.

P7 shared, “Local journalists try to give more local flavor to their news. Sometimes, we still report national news, but when we write about it, we provide local context so people here in Western Visayas can relate to the news story.”

P3 said, “We have a different perspective on how we see stories. That is why local journalists provide more contextualized stories compared to national newspapers.”

Imperialism exists even today in digital journalism, especially considering the disparity between national and local journalists. National journalists tend to undermine the capacity of local journalists simply because they are stationed and working in the province. The sad reality of working in the region does not impede the local journalists from performing their responsibilities as professional journalists. This social inequality experience by local journalists somehow affects their morale, and they may feel inferior to the national journalists. Such incidents have little implication for how multimedia journalists write their news stories. However, local journalists know they are as capable as the national journalists. The writing and communication skills of the local journalists are at par and sometimes even better than the national journalists.

P3 shared, “Journalists from Manila think they are better than us. But for me, we can do their job better. We even speak and write English better than them! But this is the sad reality of living in the province.”

Moreover, local journalists can better contextualize the story than national journalists. Sadly, there are instances when national journalists think they know better than the local journalists, even if they know that the locals should know their history better. Local journalists are stationed in the province, so they are well-updated and informed of the events happening around their area. They also know the history of the different personalities involved in the news story. By having this fundamental history of the area, the local journalists have an advantage in providing a more affluent background and in-depth context of the news story.

P1 mentioned, “When national journalists write our stories, it’s as if they know more than us, but in fact, they don’t know our history.”

The New Challenges

Today's biggest challenge for multimedia journalists is to hone their skills in **technology** since it will help them tremendously with their journalistic practices. Technology can help ease multimedia journalists' digital news gathering and writing process. Various technological developments can make the practices of multimedia journalists more efficient and convenient. They must learn how to navigate their gadgets and utilize their purpose to help them in digital newsgathering.

P7 narrated, "You have to learn how to use gadgets. You can appreciate technology if you know how to use it. It's easy to do research and monitor news online.

In this crucial period in Philippine media history, journalism is tested by evolving news consumption habits, technological advancements, and authority-threatening criticisms (Balod & Hameleers, 2021). The changes and challenges in the practices of Filipino journalists in Western Visayas brought about by the digital age profoundly implicate the world of news writing. To keep up with societal changes, multimedia journalists must get out of their comfort zone and explore the digital age. In this way, they can challenge their skills and upgrade their competencies to remain competitive in serving the interest of the local readers.

P8 emphasized, "You have to learn technology because you don't have a choice, you have to keep up with the development in society."

Mobile journalism also proves to be a rising trend in digital journalism. Multimedia journalists can now capture, create, and publish news content by only using mobile devices. With this, multimedia journalists should learn how to be tech-savvy and, more importantly, be comfortable using mobile devices while undergoing news writing. Multimedia journalists in Western Visayas see mobile journalism as a

positive development in news writing. It allows them to move freely around the area and do their job conveniently. They can also function effectively even if they are not physically present in the newsroom as long as they have their mobile devices, they can interact with their colleagues through digital space.

P5 shared, “Mobile journalism is actually a rising trend right now because of technology. Dapat equip ka gid with the latest trend in technology and you have skill in using social media. (It's essential that you equip yourself with the latest technology trend and have skills in using social media).”

Staying relevant today is as important and challenging for multimedia journalists in Western Visayas. Multimedia journalists must reinvent themselves to become more relatable to the audience. They should be willing to try new and learn things to offer something new to the digital audience. They should not be stuck up to their old routines, or else they will be left behind by younger generations of multimedia journalists. The world of journalism continues to evolve, with the competition getting stiffer and stiffer. That’s why multimedia journalists must be more adaptable and flexible to the changes.

P6 reiterated, “You have to be open to changes and innovation.”

With innovation comes new journalistic practices. Nowadays, multimedia journalists should be tech-savvy in packaging content with enticing graphic designs. They should also be well-trained in photojournalism to stay relevant mainly to the digital (SAS) audience.

P7 shared, “Now we have to learn photojournalism and graphics.”

Some multimedia journalists are also willing to explore vlogging and blogging to stay relevant and utilize their influence in reaching the public. However, even if

they are innovating their routines, their journalistic principles remain the same, only providing the digital audience with factual, reliable, and credible information.

P8 narrated, “It’s a personal decision to innovate and to reinvent yourself. I always believe in reinvention. I like trying new things because this is also part of learning or educating yourself. I actually tried blogging and created my YouTube channel, but my contents are not just any topic. I still go for substance and facts.”

The last challenge for local journalists today is their **economic situation**. Local journalists’ salaries are lower than national journalists. This challenge tempts journalists to commit malpractice or shift careers because there is no money in journalism. This is a sad reality for the local journalists that needs the utmost attention from the local government.

Robles (2019) said journalism is one of the lower-paying jobs in third-world nations, particularly in the provinces and rural areas. Multimedia journalists in Western Visayas pointed out their salaries are relatively low compared to national journalists. Moreover, Hughes et al. (2017) said in emerging democracies, severe socioeconomic inequality and financial constraints have a more significant impact on journalists' work. These unfortunate circumstances tend to influence their journalistic practices and comment that only those with strength in their character and passion for serving the people remain true to their profession.

P3 mentioned, “Honestly, the editor's salary here in Western Visayas is just the same as what the newbie reporter is receiving in Manila. There is really a disparity in the salary between local and national journalists. Truth is journalists are also being oppressed with the economic situation here in the province.”

Additionally, multimedia journalists are not celebrities who rake in a large amount of money. They are defenders of truth whose main priority is to provide the

public with relevant and essential information that may affect their lives. They are not endorsers of products or companies who have massive influence because of their celebrity status. But instead, multimedia journalists are influential in the lives of the local people because of their valuable contribution to shaping and developing society.

P4 remarked, “If you want to get rich, do not become a journalist!”

P8 shared, “the salary disparity is high comparing the national and local journalists. So if you want to get rich, don’t be a journalist, you’ll end up heartbroken and corrupt because you’ll be tempted.”

Corrupt Journalists

Corruption in media still exists for some journalists in Western Visayas even today. Although, it should be emphasized that there are still local journalists who stay true to their principles and are not accepting money from personalities or agencies. The term “envelopemental journalism” coined by local journalists, refers to multimedia journalists who receive cash in exchange for work favors.

In a world where anyone may be a publisher—but not necessarily a journalist—how the journalist executes their job will be necessary to whether that position continues to uphold any value or even exist (Friend & Singer, 2015). Corruption in media deeply and immensely implicates objectivity in news writing. Once multimedia journalists receive money, it is tantamount to silencing the freedom of the press because the news story is already bought by one party.

P3 condoned “envelopemental journalism and states corruption in media exists. This is where journalists receive money in an envelope and of course it

affects how they write their stories. I don't want people to see me as a paid journalist controlled by a particular politician or personality."

Digital media editors highly condemn corruption in media. They constantly remind their journalists not to engage in this kind of malpractice since it will affect their journalistic values. Moreover, they guide and mentor new journalists to avoid this temptation in media. They want to emphasize to the newbies that engaging in such activities could reprimand them and may face severe consequences from the media organization.

P4 also condoned envelopemental journalism and reiterated, "I always remind my reporters never to accept money. Once I discovered and proved that they received money, they are out." P 4 further, "receiving money will lose the trust and confidence of the people in you as a journalist, and this is tantamount to you being sucked in your job. It's difficult to write stories if you are receiving money from the person. How will you criticize the person, if you are receiving money from him? How can you write a balance story, if you are receiving money from that person? And to tell you honestly, here in Negros, we are now very few who are not receiving money. Some other journalists are already in the payroll of the city hall."

P8 shared, "in our station, first time you will be caught for envelopemental journalism you will be fired. Just imagine if you will interview 5 personalities, and you receive money from the 3 of them. You can decide to highlight the 3 and just kill the statements of the other 2. So in a way, you shouldn't give a chance to society to suspect or doubt your objectivity and credibility."

Hierarchy of Influences in the News Writing Process

Individual level

This study identified the possible *influences* when journalists write their news stories today. Multimedia journalists do not have absolute freedom of the press. Personal bias is at the top of the hierarchy of influences when journalists write their stories today. However, journalists should strive to remain objective, especially in the digital age, and minimize their personal biases as much as possible. Multimedia journalists have an innate calling of the content they sincerely believe in. These personal biases can adversely affect how journalists perceive things. While acknowledging that neutrality may be pointless due to the journalist's inherent biases, they still prioritize fairness and accuracy in their reporting (Balod & Hameleers, 2021). Filipino journalists must set aside their personal biases or judgments when writing their news stories. Their news stories should not reflect their preferences, or the public will accuse them of siding with one party.

P1 shared, "I can say wala kaming absolute freedom. (I can say that we do not have absolute freedom.) Journalists have their own biases. I have my personal biases where my stories tend to lean on."

Tully et al. (2020) suggest that journalists recognize that their personal biases shape their news content and news production. Furthermore, Friend and Singer (2015) argue that journalists should not harbor any hidden agenda toward any personality or agency. Journalists must uphold ethical values that define their objective reporting and news writing. Personal values and characteristics matter (Reese, 2019), especially in digital journalism. They should remain objective in presenting the news stories to the local readers. The multimedia journalists' traits,

core values, and beliefs deeply influence how reports will be given to the digital audience.

P2 said, “We do have our biases, for example, we do have an innate bias for the truth, for justice, and against propaganda. Long and short, journalists have their own biases. Although journalists have biases, but the journalistic process is objective. That objective process supposedly lessens the bias of the individual.”

More importantly, multimedia journalists' biases can influence the news writing process. However, they should be loyal to the truth and the people they serve. Ultimately, how the news story will be written and published will still depend on the journalists. This is why the personal level is at the top of the hierarchy of influence because the news will be at the mercy of multimedia journalists no matter where their personal bias is. What's important is for multimedia journalists to remain neutral and objective in writing and presenting the news story to the local readers.

P5 argued, “You should write stories based on your own truth. I follow what I think is the truth and the truth that I see and write stories about the truth that the people needs to know. In the end, it still depends on the journalist on how he decides to write his story.”

Routine level

The custom of implicitly understanding the audience's behavior relates to the routine level that influences the practices of multimedia journalists. Multimedia journalists' fundamental training in writing news stories covers understanding their audience's behavior as part of their journalistic routine. It is considered an unwritten rule that multimedia journalists clearly understand the public they serve. Their practices and styles in news gathering and writing would depend highly on the digital

(SAS) audience. This routine is significantly more important because of the current changes and development in the media landscape.

The investigative process also highlights and distinguishes the value of professional multimedia journalists compared to other content generators. This posits that undergoing rigorous investigation has an immense influence on news writing. Multimedia journalists understand that the vetting process is crucial in digital newsgathering. Moreover, multimedia journalists uphold ethics and principles when conducting proper investigations and fact-checking. They know that they should not write stories that are not verified and fact-checked. Part of their journalistic routine is ensuring they do not rely on only one source but instead have multiple sources to verify facts and information. This routine could eventually define the credibility of the news story.

The writing styles of multimedia journalists also vary from each other, and it influences one's practice. Their educational background, core competencies, and daily routines may influence how multimedia journalists package their news content. Moreover, multimedia journalists' ability to adapt to technological advancement has a noticeable advantage affecting the practices of multimedia journalists. Their capability to utilize digital technology and social media could make their practice more manageable and flexible. These changes could ease and implicate the output of multimedia journalists.

Unfortunately, some multimedia journalists are involved in corruption, which significantly influences news writing. Receiving money in exchange for work favor can tarnish the credibility of multimedia journalists and can diminish the authority of the local news media organization. Corruption in media can tempt multimedia journalists, especially since their economic situation is not good in Western Visayas.

Succumbing to temptations can yield biased reporting and news writing resulting in one-sided news stories. Incorporating self-regulatory systems and enhancing professional ethics and standards are two ways to combat corruption.

Social Media

The changes in the new media landscape influence journalists' practices since they have to adjust to societal developments to stay relevant and cater to the needs and demands of the digital audience. The reach and extent of social media influence implicate multimedia journalists' practices. Nowadays, news stories can be shared worldwide instantly, so journalists should be careful in posting them because of the repercussions it might implicate the people. The spreading of news is different and slower in traditional media. The local readers still have to wait for the regular programming and schedule on TV or radio before they can be updated with news and current affairs. However, with social media, local readers can be updated anytime and anywhere by staying connected online. The digital audience also becomes a spreader of news online by sharing the news content on their social media accounts.

The study of Westlund (2013) argues that the emergence of new media allows a massive opportunity to reach users anytime and anywhere using their mobile devices. With this development in the media landscape, news organizations are investing in digital platforms and increasing their presence in the new media. Although, Domingo et al. (2015) highlight that most news comes from reputable news outlets, including information shared on new media. Social media's reach is much more extensive in the digital age than in traditional platforms. New media are

an increasingly significant news source, revolutionizing how people experience news (Mitchell & Page, 2015).

P5 narrated, “Nowadays, you can access the news anytime and anywhere because of the internet. But before, it was very limited because of the reach of TV, radio, or newspapers. People can now access the story online and stay informed about current events.”

Sadly, the digital audience tends to spread negative news compared to positive stories. The culture of today’s generation is interested in stories full of action, regardless of whether it’s facts or fake news. This trend is rampant, especially for local readers who are not critical of consuming news content. They do not fact-check and verify sources before sharing news stories on their social media accounts. This proves to be dangerous since the reach of social media is vast and expansive, thus affecting more people.

This digital audience behavior influences the practice of multimedia journalists' because now they must respond and react to crucial matters, especially if the news content is untrue. Multimedia journalists should ensure that the public’s reaction results only from reliable, factual, and verified information.

P8 argued, “You know, it’s very fast, the reach of social media is exponential, it’s like a virus. However, what’s sad in our culture now is, everything that is negative gets shared, and anything suspicious or unbelievable they are the one that is getting enough attention. This is very alarming because these information consumers are the young ones.”

Digital News Editors, Managers, and Media Owners

It is also essential to have a digital media editor validating the accuracy of the information in the article, ensuring a good news story. Nowadays, digital media editors strongly influence news story production by weighing its news value. With the experience and expertise of digital media editors, it cannot be disregarded that they know the digital audience and the qualities of the local readers. Being in the journalistic field for many years made them highly familiar with the types of news content their local readers are patronizing. With this in mind, digital media editors have pre-set values for the news materials they seek. These standards somehow dictate the news content selected and published online. Sometimes, digital news editors depend on the core value of the news media organization they are affiliated with. No matter how good and significant the news story is, if it does not align with the core values of the digital media editor or the news media outlet, there will be tendencies that it will not make the final cut in the news production process.

P5 asserted, "Other stations have their own inclination of stories, so it depends on the news organization and the editors - what stories to publish."

Multimedia journalists acknowledge the critical function of digital media editors in any media organization. An editor may opt to change or reject a gruesome photo and instead choose a different image that complements the news story without sensationalizing it (Friend & Singer, 2015). Digital media editors also have the power to change or edit parts of the news story based on their judgment. They can edit some parts of the story and choose to reframe it into their likeness. Although there are instances that they comment on the article and let the multimedia journalists reframe their stories according to the suggestion of the digital media editor. Milojević and Krstić (2018) established that the editors' personal opinions impact the

newsroom practices. However, these are just influences in the news writing process, and it is still up to multimedia journalists to decide on the specific details of their news stories. They adhere to the digital media editors' philosophies and journalistic practices. With this, the digital media editor's influence in the news writing process is an established and acknowledged practice in the digital newsroom.

P9 shared, "I don't have control over that (stories to publish) because we have our editors who get to decide what story to publish."

Social Institutions

Another level that influences multimedia journalists' practice is the media organization they work with. Even though media organizations influence the news writing process, it is not that high compared to the personal biases of the journalists. Media organizations may suggest and recommend to their reporters the angle and content of the story. Ultimately, it's still up to the journalist how he will write and finish his story. However, the considerable role of the editors cannot be eliminated in the news writing process today.

According to Reese (2019), the organizational level acknowledges that news is produced by media outlets with their own economic and political priorities. However, media organizations must balance commercial business and professional endeavors. Hanitzsch et al. (2010) articulate that the immediate work environment, organizational frameworks, and newsroom dynamics also limit the practice of journalism. Moreover, the journalists are fully aware of the editorial policies established by their media organizations (Milojević & Krstić, 2018). Additionally, Usher (2014) observed that news production in media organizations remains unchanged despite significant technological shifts. These organizations' boundaries

are becoming more permeable as they develop collaborative partnerships. They now take on various fresh, emergent forms, from the massive daily news-gathering operation to the small-staff investigative process (Reese & Shoemaker, 2016). National news outlets have minimal influence on the news writing practices of the local journalists since they work independently.

P2 argued, “Let’s admit it, editors are dictators. You cannot produce a news story if the editors do not know how the reporters did it. For me, there’s nothing wrong with it, especially if the editors know ethical journalism.”

P3 shared, “Sometimes the news media organization I am working with like this and that. I guess there’s a small influence on how I write my stories, but it’s just minimal.”

External influences include government agencies, political figures, corporations, and businesses. These social institutions have minimal influence on the practices of multimedia journalists today because their loyalty remains to the people. Their job is to write stories about what is happening around them regardless of whose agency will be affected. Other agencies, private companies, and influential political figures as news sources were among them Reese (2019).

P2 suggested, “that the new reporters should bear with the external influences until they begin to internalize the ethical practices of news writing.”

P7 shared, “Hindi maiiwasan that there will be other agencies who will ask favors not be too harsh on them. Pero para sa kin, it’s our job to simply write what happened. As long as they gave their consent, and you have all the facts and information that you need, wala ka dapat ikatakot sa mga external influences. (It’s unavoidable that other agencies will ask favors not to be too harsh on them. As long

as you have their consent, and you have the complete information, you don't need to be afraid of writing your story.)”

Social Systems Level

Multimedia journalists can remain relevant through the quality of information they give the public. The journalists' role in building society is irreplaceable, so they should stay true to their craft by providing only factual and necessary information to make the public well-informed about what's happening around them. By doing this, multimedia journalists can remain relevant because of the value of the information they provide to society. As long as people see the journalists' critical function as a trusted and credible source of information, they will remain relevant and significant to the community. However, once the public's trust is broken, it will be difficult for multimedia journalists to stay relevant, especially with the adverse impact of social media on the perception of the digital audience.

P2 emphasized, “I think we can become relevant if we continue to provide context to the people. If we continue providing accurate and reliable information, we stay relevant.”

Additionally, multimedia journalists can remain relevant if the information they provide to the digital audience is for their safety and security. The digital audience always wants to keep themselves updated to protect their family and loved ones from unforeseen circumstances. They rely on multimedia journalists to provide information that might affect their day-to-day activities.

P4 said, “You give them relevant information that they need in their daily living. We provide them with stories they need for safety, relevant to their needs, etc. In short, just offer them the information they need daily, so you can stay relevant.”

It is also critical for multimedia journalists to build a close relationship with the community and the people around them. They should always put the concerns of the people at the top of their priority. Suppose the local people feel sincere empathy from the multimedia journalists, they will remain relevant to the public because of their genuine concern to be involved in the development of the society.

P6 shared, "You stay relevant by being involved with the concerns of society. If you don't get involved, you become irrelevant. So you stay relevant by writing stories that concern the people."

News Writing Framework in the New Media

This study developed a news writing framework in the new media derived from the practices of Filipino journalists in Western Visayas (Figure 1).

This framework emphasizes that news writing begins with understanding the digital (SAS) audience. The new media landscape evolved with the proliferation of digital technology, and so does the behavior and attitude of news consumers. Journalists must understand the behavior of the digital audience to meet their needs and demands. The digital audience is more graphically oriented and prefers to consume news with photos and videos. With this, contemporary journalists must include good-quality photos and videos in their news stories. Most common news content still revolves around human interest and any activities concerning their day-to-day activities.

Journalists must find newsworthy stories about people and happenings that might implicate their lives and society. Moreover, the proliferation of new media allows the public to participate in news production by generating, producing, and disseminating news content. This framework posits that the digital audience dictates

what news content the public needs, and thus they also choose what types of news stories to consume.

Figure 1 News Writing Framework in the New Media

Newsworthy stories are usually centered around people and the community. Journalists can find information anywhere and at any time of the day, so they need to be on the ground and do the investigation. Journalists must also be diligent in finding news stories and know how to spot and follow leading news content. Furthermore, the introduction of digital technology and new media made news gathering much

easier, faster, and more accessible. Journalists can now communicate with their sources using their mobile devices and technology. The internet also paved the way for easier access to big data and documents, making the research process more convenient and cheaper for journalists. However, the explosion of fake news and disinformation comes with the advent of social media and its massive influence on people. Journalists must stand guard in protecting the public from fake news and battling disinformation.

This framework also suggests that the tedious process of verification and fact-checking is required in the news gathering, writing, and selecting of the stories to be produced. It is imperative to do fact-checking and verify the information before a journalist starts writing their news story. The verification process is vital to ensure that the news story will be devoid of inaccuracies and errors. Without this practice, the journalist cannot be called a real journalist. The real journalist should not settle with only one source but verify the information's veracity with multiple sources. It's an arduous task, but it's the responsibility of the journalists to ensure that their news stories are accurate, credible, and have only verified information.

Once the journalists have complete, factual, and verified information, they can start building up and writing their news stories. Journalists have varied techniques and strategies for presenting their news stories. They should know how to find a good angle to offer the story interestingly so the digital audience will be hooked to read and finish their news stories. Journalists should also learn to be independent of external influences and, most importantly, shy away from their biases and judgment. This study posits that journalists' personal biases greatly influence their writing styles. Although, this study does not disregard the factors of external level having minimal influence on their news writing practices. Ultimately, this study highlights that

no matter where your biases are, journalists should practice being objective and write stories according to the truth. Moreover, because of the proliferation of new media, journalists must be cautious in their practices because of the emergence of cybercrimes and cyber libel. Additionally, utilizing modern technology to edit offline and online news stories made the news writing process quicker and more efficient.

Finally, this framework depicts that news content selection in the new media landscape for publication depends on the editor and the news media organization. This study suggests that editors and news media organizations have the last say in selecting what news stories to be published. The media organization also controls the type of published news since the editors should approve all news stories. This framework also suggests that a report cannot be published if it does not contain complete information and unverified facts. News stories must be balanced and provide all sides of the story. This could increase the chances of being selected, especially if the news concerns the people and significantly impacts their lives and society.

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

This study described the current practices of nine Filipino journalists in Western Visayas in the new media landscape, how it implicates objectivity in news production, and the influences affecting the news writing process. The journalistic practices in the new media are summed as the following (1) Understanding the “SAS” (Short Attention Span) Audience, (2) Digital News Gathering, (3) Fact-finders, (4) Multimedia Journalists, (5) Digital Media Editors, and (6) Safeguarding in the New Media.

This study reiterates the importance of understanding the digital (SAS) audience as the baseline foundation in the news writing process. The emergence of new media and the advancement of technology changed the audience's behavior, especially in news consumption. It is critical that journalists genuinely understand their audience to meet their needs and demands in staying relevant to democracy and society. Having a short attention span and the massive competition in news content made journalism more challenging, especially in the digital age. Multimedia journalists should learn to adapt to the demands of the SAS audience to remain relevant and significant in building society. Moreover, the presentation of news content has evolved due to the proliferation of new media. Digital (SAS) audience proves to be more graphically and visually oriented, demanding good-quality photo or short video recording alongside a very brief and concise news description.

Secondly, this study found that journalists adapted digital technologies to make the news-gathering process more convenient and efficient. Technology made

communicating with the public and doing investigative work through mobile devices accessible and cheaper. More importantly, traditional and contemporary journalists know the importance of undergoing the arduous tasks of vetting and fact-checking, which distinctly identify them from social media influencers. The internet and digital technology revolutionized the news gathering, writing, and dissemination of news content. Multimedia journalists should be careful in building their sources and screening the information they gather, especially with the advent of fake news and peddlers of disinformation.

Furthermore, journalists should verify all the facts and information before writing and releasing their news stories. This study highlights the importance of the verification process, more importantly with the advent of new media. They are not disinformation peddlers and should provide the people with only credible, verified, and confirmed facts. The digital audience still sees journalists and new media organizations as the number one plausible source of news and information despite the numerous attempts to silence their influence in shaping society.

Once the journalists have verified all the facts and gathered all sides of the story, they can begin building their write-ups and writing their stories. Filipino journalists in Western Visayas have different writing styles and techniques in today's digital age. Multimedia journalists should be brief, concise, and direct to the point in presenting their news content. The digital audience expects more from multimedia journalists, demanding more creative, enticing, and engaging news content. Multimedia journalists should learn photojournalism and invest in digital gadgets since the digital (SAS) audience is leaning towards consuming news online.

Although, there is no absolute freedom in journalism even today, and every journalist has their own biases. Contemporary journalists should find ways to set

aside their prejudices and make sure that their news stories will be free from them. News stories should only bear information that the people need to make informed decisions about their life and society.

This study also articulates the critical role of the editors and the news media organization in selecting the news stories to be selected and published for the digital audience's consumption. Digital media editors serve as the safety net filtering the news content that is significant and relevant to the digital audience. They also mentor newbie journalists guiding them to uphold their values and correct practices. Digital media editors must see the value of the news content so it can be selected to be published in the online newspaper.

Moreover, this study reiterates the importance of media accountability, especially in today's digital media landscape. Digital audiences are critical of journalists who publish false stories and articles with errors and unverified facts. With the reach and influence of social media, journalists must correct their errors immediately, or else it is effortless for their reputations to be destroyed. Taking responsibility for their mistakes is essential since the digital audience sees multimedia journalists as the person with authority. It is also critical that local news organizations put up strict policies and protocols in dealing with errors and mistakes.

Moving on with the practices that implicate objectivity in news writing in the new media, this study narrated them in the following (1) New Media landscape, (2) Gatekeeper of Truth and Democracy, (3) Local and National News Agencies Today, (4) The New Challenges, and (5) Corrupt Journalists.

The media landscape has evolved because social media makes traditional print media thrive. The social media reach, and influence is exponential, posing a more significant challenge for journalists to be cautious with their profession.

Journalists today should work together to fight disinformation and fake news that could adversely affect people's lives and society. With the advent of social media, the digital audience already shifted their preference for consuming information online rather than in printed newspapers. With these developments, multimedia journalists must adapt to new media and adjust their practices implicating their objectivity in news writing.

Multimedia journalists also prove to be at the forefront of gatekeeping the truth and democracy in the country. Multimedia journalists must stay faithful to their calling of keeping the public well-educated, informed, and aware of the events around them. Through this practice, multimedia journalists become debunkers of false information and advocates for defending democracy. They should guard against peddlers of disinformation and influential people who aim to silence the media and protect their interests.

National journalists have little influence in the news writing process in Western Visayas since local journalists work independently. However, the noticeable disparity in their practice points to local journalists having more heart and soul for local news. Local journalists can provide better contextualization since they know their history better and have better backgrounds than national journalists. Sadly though, local journalists receive significantly lower salaries than national journalists. This sad reality implicates multimedia journalists' objectivity since they can be tempted to accept bribes and money in exchange for work favors.

Additionally, this study highlighted the new challenges for journalists, such as honing their skills in using technology, improving their skills to stay relevant to the people, and overcoming the issues of the economic situation related to their profession.

Finally, this study argues that corruption in media still exists even today because of the economic situation of the local journalists working in the province. Such malpractices ultimately influence the practices of Filipino journalists, implicating their objectivity in writing news stories.

The hierarchy of influence proves to be relevant in understanding journalistic practices even in today's media landscape. The personal level still proves to be at the top of the hierarchy of influence owing to the inherent biases of multimedia journalists. Multimedia journalists have innate biases from their experiences, individual traits, and beliefs. However, these biases should be avoided to make the news story balance and viable for the digital audience.

Routine levels also influence the news writing process since these are unwritten rules the multimedia journalists consciously and subconsciously follow. The repeated practice of multimedia journalists dictates how the news writing process is being accomplished in the world of journalism.

This study added the massive influence of social media in the hierarchy of influence. Social media's exponential reach influences how multimedia journalists write and present news content. Multimedia journalists should be cautious with their practice since social media can easily implicate them through trolls and bashers. The proliferation of social media also changed the behavior of the digital audience since they became more obsessed with their mobile devices. With these developments in the digital age, multimedia journalists must hone their skills in using social media.

Digital media editors and networks still influence news production even in the digital age. They are still the one who filters and selects the news content that will be published online. Multimedia journalists must first pass the eagle eyes of digital media editors before presenting their news stories to the digital audience. The digital

media editors also mentor and guide newbie journalists, influencing their journalistic foundation and principles.

Social institutions such as private institutions, companies, and other agencies have minor influence on news writing unless multimedia journalists sacrifice their principles and accept bribes. Multimedia journalists in Western Visayas are loyal to the local people and the truth.

Lastly, multimedia journalists serve the interconnected groups of society. Their practice paves the way for the community to stay strong and help each other develop. Multimedia journalists must provide only factual information so the people and the community will have a better society.

Conclusions

The following points were concluded based on the findings of this study:

The news writing process of Filipino journalists has evolved because of the emergence of new media. Technology and mobile devices revolutionized the news writing process, which involves gathering, writing, and selecting news content. Technology makes their practice more straightforward and more manageable. It was also concluded that Filipino journalists value the importance of fact-checking, verification, and investigation process in the digital age that uniquely distinguishes them from social media influencers. This study also concludes that the personal level is at the top of the hierarchy of influence in digital journalism. This study reiterates that it is still up to the journalists to decide what information to include and how to present the news stories.

Moreover, this study concludes that the emergence of new media considerably impacted objectivity in news writing. As the world leans towards the

digital age, so as the media landscape. The reach and influence of the new media cannot be undermined in shaping the digital audience's worldview perspectives. Finally, it was concluded that the biggest challenge today for contemporary journalists is to fight disinformation, safeguard the truth, and stay loyal to the people by ensuring objectivity in their practices.

Recommendations

The following points are recommended based on the findings of this study:

- (1) In today's digital age, it was established that technology plays a vital role in the news writing process in the new media. With this, it is recommended that contemporary journalists learn to hone their social media skills and be more adept at using technology to cope with the demands of the digital audience.
- (2) The digital (SAS) audience proves to demand more visuals in the news content. With this, it is recommended that multimedia journalists invest in studying photojournalism to make their practice more adept in meeting the demands of the digital audience. Moreover, photojournalism can also be highlighted as a major subject in the school curriculum since this proves to be the demand of the digital audience.
- (3) Since this study concluded that one of the most prominent roles of journalists today is to fight disinformation, especially with the advent of new media. Media organizations and other civic groups are recommended to try to fight disinformation. It is essential that various societal groups would help each other battle disinformation because it has a massive implication in molding our society today.

- (4) This study found that local media outlets are not stringent in dealing with errors, even with digital technology. With this, it is recommended that media outlets should have clear and transparent policies in dealing with errors to make their journalists more accountable for their journalistic practices in the new media.
- (5) Future study is recommended to explore the world of bloggers and describe their practices and how they uphold objectivity in their news content.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Dear Research Participants,

Greetings. This study entitled, **UNDERSTANDING NEWS WRITING IN THE DIGITAL AGE: A NARRATIVE INQUIRY INTO THE PRACTICES OF FILIPINO JOURNALISTS IN WESTERN VISAYAS**, is aimed at describing the practices of Filipino journalists in Western Visayas like you.

Kindly read the details for the study enumerated below so that you can ask questions, should there be any.

The Researchers

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this study is to explore the practices of Filipino journalists in Western Visayas and describe the news writing process. Moreover, this study will also identify and narrate the changes in the journalistic practices of news writing brought about by the digital age.

Benefits of the Study

While this research does not give you any direct benefit, your participation in this study will be specifically insightful in determining key information on the world of news writing.

Duration

The online interview via Zoom may take forty five (45) to sixty (60) minutes of your time.

Risks of the Study

You may have to share some personal information that will make you feel uncomfortable. Should this happen, know that you may not have to answer or take part in the interview, especially if you feel that the questions are too personal. Please let us know of any unintended harm either through our Contact Details +639611612479 or gsagala@usa.edu.ph so that we can ask for the assistance of an expert in this field.

Confidentiality, Privacy, and Anonymity

Confidentiality, Privacy, and Anonymity will be ensured in the collection, storage, and publication of this research material. All data and information collected will be used solely for academic pursuits. The data generated will be kept secured in paper or electronic form for a period of one year after the completion of the study.

Voluntary Participation

As participation is entirely voluntary on your part, you may or may not take part in this study. Should you decide not to participate, please know that nothing changes in any or all of your employee-related evaluations. If you withdraw at any time, you may do so. Should you decide to participate, you may fill out and sign the Consent Certificate or signify "Yes" verbally during the online interview, before proceeding to the interview proper.

CONSENT CERTIFICATE

_____ I confirm that the study was fully explained to me; also, I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study and I have had the opportunity to ask questions.

_____ I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.

_____ I agree to take part in the above study.

Signature of the Participant

APPENDIX B

JOURNALISTIC PRACTICES WITH THE ADVENT OF NEW MEDIA						
Line SN	Participants	Statements	Coding	Initial Theme	Sub Themes	Final Themes
Line 1049	P 4	It's not anymore what I like, but what the public like.	Not what I like	Audience preference	Audience behavior	Understanding "SAS" (Short Attention Span) Audience
Line 1050	P 4	It will not work, that I will write only the information that I want to give them.	Not what I like	Journalists preference		
Line 1051	P 4	I have to give the people the information they like and the information they need.	Information they like & need	Audience preference		
Line 1052	P 4	So it's really important that you study your market and you understand your audience.	Understand the audience	Study the audience		
Line 1509	P 8	And we have a very young, very restless, very distracted, and uninformed audience.	Audience characteristics	Audience profile		
Line 1518	P 8	So we have to learn and understand what people like. That's why nowadays, no one writes too long essays anymore.	Understand the audience	Audience preference		
Line 1522	P 8	So why will I argue with that? It's what the audience like. In short, I have to really consider my audience and change my journalistic practice to suit their needs and demands.	Audience preference	Audience preference		
Line 470	P 1	Because of the improvement in technology, mas damo kame gadgets to use which make the work lighter (we have more gadgets to use which make the work lighter)	More gadget to use	Advantage of using technology	News gathering using technology	Digital News Gathering
Line 471	P 1	We can now use mobile phones to contact more people. Hindi na budlay magcontact sa mga tawo! (It's now easier to contact different people). Our sources became more accessible as well.	Easier to contact sources	Advantage of using technology		
Line 472	P 1	Sa ngayon, hindi na kinanglan maglakad ng pila ka-oras or magsaka sa bukid, kay macontact mo na imo source thru cellphone. (Nowadays, we do not need to walk or go to far flung areas, because we can just call our sources through our cellphone.)	Access to sources	Advantage of using technology		
Line 475	P 2	In short, news gathering became faster and easier. But still, we still have to collect information and verify our facts same as the traditional way.	Faster & easier	Advantage of using technology		

Line 1365	P 8	In the newsroom we also monitor our competitors and the national news.	Monitor competitors	Monitor news online	
Line 1366	P 8	And also what's happening internationally. And also online news.	Happening around	Monitor news online	
Line 1368	P 8	Because you cannot be left behind, so you have to stay updated with what's happening around you.	Happening around	Monitor news online	
Line 1604	P 9	With regards to sources, before you really have to go out and get documents on different locations, but now you can easily download press releases, official documents from the government, and other related documents online.	Access to information	Downloading of documents	
Line 509	P 2	If we go to the basic journalistic principle, there's a saying - you have to give the people what they need to know, but you also have to give them what they should know	Need & should know	Human interest	Newsworthy content in the digital age
Line 507	P 2	It should concerned everyone from politics, development issues, insurgencies, local context like local and economic concerns.	Public interests		
Line 508	P 2	For example local sugar industry crimes, peace and order. These are the things of public interest.	News in local context		
Line 709	P 3	Any news about people could become good stories	News about people		
Line 708	P 3	You know, mga tao ngayon, feeling nila at sa isip nila they are celebrities. (Nowadays, everyone thinks and feel that they are celebrities.)	People think they are celebrities		
Line 1129	P 5	Unang una, is it useful for the people? (Primary consideration is will be useful for the people?)	Useful for the people		
Line 1131	P 5	Journalists should select stories that would benefit the people and give them the information they need and want.	Benefit the people		
Line 353	P 1	For example, we monitor the price of the onion ever since nag shoot-up ang iya price. We monitor ano na mga gatabo sa paligid and we write stories about it. (We monitor the price of onions ever since it's price shoot up. We monitor what is happening in the area and we write stories about it.)	Monitoring of top news happening around	Current events	

Line 356	P 1	We keep the people updated about the price hike and how the people are responding to the price hike.	How people find alternatives? Their actions.			
Line 1317	P 7	May ara man people who really want to be updated with local policies, business, traffic reports, accidents, etc. (There are people who really wants to be updated with local policies, business, traffic reports, accidents, etc.)	Local policies, business			
Line 1318	P 7	These stories also pick up because it concerns their day-to-day activities	Day to day activities			
Line 585	P 2	And I think, that diligence will win in the end	Diligence in news gathering	Diligence in news gathering	Investigative Process today	
Line 586	P 2	Because this will make your story stand out. Makita in your news story, the level of skills and diligence you put in news gathering and verifying information. (Diligence will win in the end because this will make your story stand out. The level of skills and diligence you put in news gathering and verifying information will show in your news story.)	Skill & diligence in news gathering & verification	Skills in news gathering		
Line 1429	P 8	You are not a real journalist if you don't go out there, talk to people, and cover the news.	Going out and covering the news	Investigate personally		
Line 1428	P 8	We risk our lives to cover the story, umaakyat ako ng bundok, nasugatan ako, nagsusunog ako ng kilay just to have my full story. (We risk our lives just to cover a story! I climb mountains, got bruises, and working overtime just to have my full story.)	Risking our lives to cover the news	Investigate personally		
Line 1481	P 8	Iba talaga when you ask questions because you'll know the whole story and how you'll write your news story. (It's really different when you personally asked the question because you'll know the whole story and how you'll write the news story.)	You are the one asking questions	Personally asking question		
Line 392	P 1	Another example, hindi ako naga-rely only on press releases, I checked the information on my sources on the ground.	Do not rely only on press releases	Press releases	Fact-checking	Fact-finders

Line 396	P 1	For example, may ara accident reports, makadto ko sa hospital and ask the victims what really happened. I ask them if ok ba sila? Are they all safe? (For example, there's an accident, I'll go to the hospital and ask the victims what really happened, are they ok, are they all safe?)	I go and ask the people on the ground	Ask questions		
Line 397	P 1	Hindi ako basta lang magpati sa kung ano mga ginahambal ng pulis. (I do not just believe what the police are saying.)	Do not simply believe what police is saying	Ask questions		
Line 590	P 2	You know, in our social media, we received many messages, photos, and videos.	Verify facts and information	Verify information		
Line 591	P 2	And when we think the story is interesting, we call the sender and ask where they got the photos.	Receiving lots of messages in social media	Call the source		
Line 592	P 2	May ara incident, na ang sender sends photo na hindi man sa kanila. They got it from the internet, and they send it to us. (There are instances that the sender are sending photos that are not owned by them. They got it from the internet and sending it to us.)	Senders are sending photos from the internet	Materials are not owned by the sender		
Line 953	P 4	You have to write and deal with all the senses – sight, hearing, smell, and taste.	All senses			
Line 954	P 4	Basically, you need to describe the news explicitly to your audience.	Describe all senses	Basic, simple, and understandable		
Line 955	P 4	Dapat mafeel at isipin ng audience that they are actually there with you. (Your audience should feel and think that they are actually there with you,)	Feel & think that they are actually there with you			
Line 1328	P 7	You have to rethink and also update your style in writing.	Update your style in writing			
Line 1329	P 7	Because in social media, you cannot write long stories, you have to be brief and concise. Short but with complete information.	Long stories	Short & concise	Writing style in the new media	Multimedia Journalists
Line 1519	P 8	Usually 2-3 sentences. That's it!	2-3 sentences			
Line 1520	P 8	Post a compelling photo with a 5 second video. That's what the audience want!	Short but with video			
Line 406	P 1	Also, with the use of technology, makakakuha ka na ng good quality photos and videos na pede mo magamit sa imo news story. (with the use of technology, you can have good quality pictures and videos that	Can get good quality photos & videos using technology	With photos & videos		

		you can use in your news story.)				
Line 407	P 1	Nowadays, this is really important and what the people is looking for (pictures and videos).	Interesting for the people			
Line 931	P 4	For us in digital platform, we cannot proceed without good videos even if you have a good write up, it will not work,	In digital, must have videos			
Line 933	P 4	If you have a good write-up but you don't have a video, you will be put in the least priority of news stories.	Good story, no video			
Line 934	P 4	But good story plus good video, then automatically, you will be on number 1 priority.	Good story with video			
Line 416	P 1	If the news is bad or something like a tragedy, I try to find an angle where I can show the hope of the people.	Looking for a different angle to show hope for the people	Different angle & context		
Line 417	P 1	It's also important to show their ambitions and accomplishments.	Angle to highlight ambitions & accomplishments			
Line 420	P 1	You find angle that can showcase the extent of damage it will cost to the people, not just focus on the basic information about the tragedy. This will make your news story more relatable to the audience.	Angle to show the extent of damage to people			
Line 664	P 2	Journalists provide intelligent context to the news with a sane voice. Dapat makahatag ka rason sa mga tawo to read your news. (You should give reasons to the people to read your news stories.)	Intelligent context			
Line 435	P 1	I can say wala kaming absolute freedom. (I can say that we do not have absolute freedom.)	No absolute freedom	Personal level	Influences	
Line 436	P 1	Journalists have their own biases.	Own biases			
Line 437	P 1	I have my personal biases where my stories tend to lean on. And my biases is shown in my news stories, it shows where my stand is.	Have personal bias			
Line 547	P 2	We do have biases. For example, we do have an innate bias for the truth, for justice, and against propaganda.	Innate bias for truth			

Line 550	P 2	Long and short, journalists have their own biases. Anyone who tells you, that journalists doesn't have bias are not real journalists.	Biases			
Line 551	P 2	Although the journalist have biases, but the journalist process is objective.	Process should be objective			
Line 553	P 2	That objective process is supposedly lessen the bias of the individual	Lessen the bias			
Line 1119	P 5	You should write stories based on your own truth.	Write stories based on your truth			
Line 1122	P 5	I follow what I think is the truth and the truth that I see and write stories about the truth that the people needs to know.	I follow what I think is the truth			
Line 1127	P 5	In the end, it still depends on the journalist on how he decides to write his story.	Journalists decision			
Line 562	P 2	I mean let's admit, editors are dictators.	Editors are dictators	Media organization		
Line 563	P 2	You cannot produce a news story if the editors do not know how the reporters did it.	Editors should know how you produce the story			
Line 560	P 2	And there's nothing wrong about it, especially if the editors know ethical journalism.	Editors know ethical journalism			
Line 804	P 3	Another thing, sometimes the news media organization you are working with like this and that.	News organization			
Line 806	P 3	I guess, there's a small influence in the way I write my stories, but it's just minimal	Minimal influence			
Line 566	P 2	In case of external factors, the new reporters should bear with the external influences until they begin to internalize the ethical practices of news writing.	External or newsroom	External influences		
Line 1293	P 7	Hindi maiiwasan that there will be other agencies who will ask favors not be too harsh on them. (It's unavoidable that there are other agencies who will ask favors not to be too harsh on them.)	Agencies asking favors			
Line 1294	P 7	Pero para sakin, it's our job to simply write what happened. (But for me, it's our job to simply write what happened.)	Write stories as it happened			

Line 1297	P 7	As long as they gave their consent, and you have all the facts and information that you need, wala ka dapat ikatakot sa mga external influences (As long as you have their consent, and you have the complete information, you don't need to be afraid of writing your story.)	Facts & accurate information				
Line 939	P 4	Like for example, in digital, we have copyright cases. You cannot take a photo of somebody else without asking their permission	Cannot take photo without permission	Copyright cases	Cyber crime & cyber libel		
Line 1598	P 9	There is cybercrime and cyberlibel.	Cybercrime & cyberlibel	Online cases			
Line 1600	P 9	Journalists have to take care of themselves because of the changes of the laws due to social media and the world wide web out there.	Taking care of themselves	Online cases			
Line 476	P 1	Another thing, we now have technology helping us in editing.	Editing stories	Editing stories	Editing using technology		
Line 477	P 1	It's easier to correct spelling mistakes or grammar errors because of computers.	Correct spelling mistakes & errors	Correct spellings			
Line 478	P 1	Now we are also using application that makes our work easier and looks more professional than before.	Use online applications	Online applications			
Line 1501	P 8	There is no problem with mobile journalism because we use our mobile phones and technology to post and edit our news stories.	Use mobiles to edit stories	Editing stories			
Line 1602	P 9	It's more of technicality, now everything is easier with technology.	Easier with technology	Technical differences			
Line 1603	P 9	You can copy-paste, edit your story online using your mobile phone, and even utilize word count.	Using technology	Advantage of using technology			
Line 915	P 4	So we gather everything and collects all the stories that we have.	Gather everything	Editors role	Editor's role	Digital Media Editors	
Line 916	P 4	As the editor-in-chief, I rank the news stories according to the most important ones.	Rank the stories according to importance	Editors role			
Line 917	P 4	So I got to decide which stories can make it to the top 10 most important stories.	Editors select the top 10 stories	Editors role			
Line 1130	P 5	other stations have their own inclination of stories, so it depends on the news organization and the editors - what stories to publish	Media organization & editors select news to publish	Editors role			

Line 1583	P 9	I don't have control over that (stories to publish) because we have our editors who get to decide what story to publish	No control on the stories to be selected	Editors role		
Line 755	P 3	If we committed errors, journalists should be accountable for that. We have to correct our mistakes	Accountable for errors	Media accountability	Accountability in the New Media	Safeguarding in the New Media
Line 1285	P 7	News organizations should have their policies when dealing with these kinds of things like errors, corrections, fact-checking, etc	News organization should have policies in dealing with errors	Policies for corrective errors		
Line 1286	P 7	The news organization should be transparent, so the people can understand what really happened	Transparent policies	Transparent policies on errors		
Line 1454	P 8	The reality is, not all media organizations are strict when it comes to rules and policies concerning inaccuracies and errors	Strict with their policies	Media accountability		
Line 1455	P 8	Some of them just take down their article and then that's enough.	Taking down articles	Practice of some outlets		
Line 1456	P 8	But for me, what if you post something that is unverified and there's an error with the information. What if you cause panic like stampede, trouble, or panic buying?	Cause panic	Not being accountable		
Line 1457	P 8	So that is very irresponsible on the part of media.	Irresponsible journalism	Not being accountable		
Line 1458	P 8	You cannot simply say, I took it down after 30 minute, so what?	Irresponsible journalism	Not being accountable		
Line 1459	P 8	What if in those 30 minutes you caused public outrage, and there will be casualties or chaos.	Irresponsible journalism	Not being accountable		
Line 760	P 3	When faced with errors in my news story, I issue an explanation story. For instance, stating that initially, the police thought that there were 6 deaths, but eventually, they found out that the other 2 have weak pulse but are alive.	Issued an explanation story about the error	Explanation story	Corrective actions	
Line 761	P 3	So I have to update and correct my story.	Update and correct story	Correcting the story		
Line 1115	P 5	Sa iban na station, they will write a new story and quote the previous story stating the error. (In other station, they will issue a new story and quote the previous story stating the error.)	Issue a new story	Issue a correction		

Line 1571	P 9	It's important to correct the errors immediately. Timeliness is of the essence.	Correct the errors immediately	Correcting the error		
Line 1572	P 9	You do not wait for 2 or 3 days just to correct your mistake.	Do not wait	Correcting the error		

CHANGES IN PRACTICES						
Line SN	Participants	Statements	Coding	Initial Theme	Sub Themes	Final Themes
Line 687	P 3	And I can say, that print media is a dying industry because of the emergence of new media.	Print media is dying because of new media	Thriving media	New media	
Line 688	P 3	Like in our media outlet, prepandemic, we are printing our issues like 6 days a week.	Frequency of printing	Thriving media		
Line 689	P 3	But during the pandemic, we have to cease printing.	Cease printing	Thriving media		
Line 690	P 3	Slowly, we returned now but with a new manpower, and currently we are only printing 3 times a week.	Frequency of printing	Thriving media		
Line 1610	P 9	Mainstream media thrives because of social media.	Social media	Thriving media		
Line 1623	P 9	I do not look at the changes in today's media as a bad thing.	Changes is not bad	Media is evolving		
Line 1624	P 9	Because this is how the world evolve.	Changes is not bad	Media is evolving		
Line 1159	P 5	Nowadays, you can access the news anytime and anywhere because of the internet.	Access news anytime & anywhere	Accessible online	Reach and extent of influence	New Media Landscape
Line 1160	P 5	But before, it's very limited because of the reach of tv, radio, or newspaper.	Limited in traditional	Limited access		
Line 1162	P 5	People can now access the story online and stay informed about current events.	Access news anytime & anywhere	Accessible online		
Line 1497	P 8	You know, it's very fast, the reach of social media is exponential, it's like a virus.	Reach is exponential	Massive reach		
Line 1499	P 8	What's sad in our culture now, is that everything that is negative gets shared, and anything suspicious or unbelievable, they are the one that is getting enough attention. Which is very alarming because the consumers of these information are the young ones.	Negative are being shared	Negative news are being shared		
Line 458	P 1	The role of journalists remains the same.	Remains the same	Basic journalistic role	Bigger responsibility	Gatekeeper of Truth and Democracy
Line 459	P 1	To inform, educate, and make people be aware of societal issues.	To inform, educate, and awareness	Basic journalistic role		

Line 463	P 1	It is very important that people are well-informed and updated about what's happening in their locality.	People are well-informed	Basic journalistic role		
Line 464	P 1	Lastly, I think journalists should also preserve our culture. They have to keep the history alive.	Preserve our culture	New roles		
Line 466	P 1	I'm also an advocate of Hiligaynon writing. So I encourage my colleagues to practice Hiligaynon writing to keep it alive.	Preserve our culture	New roles		
Line 868	P 3	We react on the information they publish especially if it's disinformation that can affect people's lives.	Journalists react on disinformation	Disinformation	Fighting disinformation	
Line 869	P 3	We debunk information on social media that are not true.	Debunk information	Disinformation		
Line 1036	P 4	In our country, the number one problem dito sa'ten is the spread of disinformation and fake news (the number one problem is the spread of disinformation and fake news)	Problem in PH is disinformation & fake news	Disinformation & fake news		
Line 1044	P 4	Confuse na ang mga tao which is fake and real news. (People now are confuse with what is fake and which is real)	People are confused with fake & real stories	Real & fake news		
Line 453	P 1	But in reality, it's not. Local journalists provide background to the news story.	Provide background of the story	Local context		Difference in practice
Line 454	P 1	We do not just generalize and make stories. We know more about our history, so we can provide better contextualization of what really happened.	Provide better contextualization	Local context		
Line 798	P 3	We have a different perspective on how we see stories	Different perspective	Different perspective		
Line 799	P 3	That is why local journalists provide more contextualized stories compared to national newspapers.	Provide context	Local context		
Line 1312	P 7	But local journalists here, try to give more local flavor to their news.	Local flavor to the news	Local flavor		
Line 1313	P 7	Sometimes, we still report national news, but when we write about it, we provide local context so people here in Western Visayas can relate to the news story.	Local flavor to the news	Local flavor		
Line 1591	P 9	We are more attached to the story because we have more familiarity with it. That's why we can give more context and history about the news.	Familiarity	Local flavor		

Line 452	P 1	When national journalists write our stories, it's as if they know more than us, but in fact, they don't know our history	As if they know better than local journalist	Superiority	Imperialism	
Line 843	P 3	Journalists from Manila think they are better than us.	They think they are better than local journalists	Superiority		
Line 845	P 3	But for me, we can do their job better. We even speak and write English better than them!	We can speak & write better English	Better than national journalists		
Line 846	P 3	But this is the sad reality of living in the province.	Sad reality living in the province	Provincial journalists		
Line 781	P 3	Honestly, the salary of the editor here in Western Visayas, is just receiving the same salary as a newbie reporter in Manila.	Low salary of local journalists	Low salary	Economic situation	
Line 782	P 3	So think about the disparity in the salary between the local and the national journalists.	Disparity of salary between local and national journalists	Disparity in salary		
Line 780	P 3	Truth is journalists are also being oppressed with the economic situation here in the province	Economic situation in the Philippines	Economic situation		
Line 1088	P 4	Lastly, if you want to get rich, do not become a journalist.	No money in journalism	You cannot get rich		
Line 1471	P 8	The salary disparity is high comparing national and local journalists.	Salary disparity	Salary disparity		
Line 1491	P 8	If you want to get rich, don't be a journalist, you'll end up heartbroken and corrupt.	Not to be rich	Low salary		
Line 1492	P 8	Because you'll be tempted.	You'll be tempted	Temptation		
Line 1168	P 5	Mobile journalism is actually a rising trend right now because of technology	Mobile journalism is a rising trend	Trends in new media	Technology	The New challenges
Line 1169	P 5	Dapat equip ka gid with the latest trend in technology and you have skill in using social media. (It's essential that you equip yourself with the latest trend in technology and you have skills in using social media).	Skills in social media	Social media		
Line 1323	P 7	You have to learn how to use gadgets.	Learn gadgets	Hone skills		
Line 1340	P 7	You can appreciate technology if you know how to use it.	Appreciate technology	Advantage of using technology		
Line 1341	P 7	It's easy to do research and monitor news online	Do research online	Research using technology		

Line 1516	P 8	You also have to learn technology because you don't have a choice, you have to keep up with the development in the society.	Keep up with technology	Challenge for journalist		
Line 658	P 2	I think we can become relevant if we continue to provide context to people.	Provide context to the people	Quality of information	Staying relevant	
Line 659	P 2	If we continue providing accurate and reliable information, we stay relevant.	Provide accurate & reliable information			
Line 1066	P 4	You give them relevant information that they need in their day to day living.	Relevant information to their day to day living			
Line 1069	P 4	What we did, we provide them with stories that they need for their safety, relevant to their needs, etc.	Relevant information to their day to day living			
Line 1070	P 4	Just offer them information that they need in their everyday life, so you can stay relevant.	Relevant information to their day to day living			
Line 1243	P 6	By being involved with the concerns of the society	Involved in society			
Line 1244	P 6	If you don't get involve you become irrelevant.	If not involved, becomes irrelevant			
Line 1247	P 6	So you stay relevant by writing stories that concerns the people.	Concerns the people			
Line 1258	P 6	Journalist should be open for changes and innovation.	Open for change & innovation			Open to change & innovation
Line 1324	P 7	Now we have to learn photojournalism and even graphics.	New skills			
Line 1511	P 8	It's a personal decision to innovate and to reinvent yourself.	Reinvent yourself			
Line 1512	P 8	I always believe in reinvention, I like trying new things because this is also part of learning or educating yourself.	Reinvent yourself			
Line 1513	P 8	I tried blogging and created my YouTube channel, but my contents there are not just any topic.	Reinvent yourself			
Line 768	P 3	Another thing is journalist should condone "envelopemental journalism".	Envelopemental journalism	Envelopemental journalism	Corruption in New Media	Corrupt Journalists
Line 769	P 3	Corruption in media also exist. This is where journalists receive money in an envelope and of course it affects how they write their stories.	Receiving money	Envelopemental journalism		

Line 829	P 3	I don't want people to see me as a paid journalist controlled by a particular politician or personality	Paid journalists	Envelopement al journalism
Line 1009	P 4	I always remind my reporters never to accept money.	Avoid receiving money	Envelopement al journalism
Line 1010	P 4	Once I discovered and proved that they received money, they are out.	Receiving money	Envelopement al journalism
Line 1011	P 4	This will lose the trust and confidence of the people in you as a journalist, and this is tantamount to you being sucked in your job.	Lose trust & confidence	Envelopement al journalism
Line 1012	P 4	Cause, it's quite difficult to write stories if you are receiving money from the person.	Receiving money	Envelopement al journalism
Line 1013	P 4	How will you criticize the person, if you are receiving money from him?	Receiving money	Envelopement al journalism
Line 1014	P 4	How can you write a balance story, if you are receiving money from that person?	Balance of the story	Envelopement al journalism
Line 1015	P 4	To tell you honestly, here in Negros, we are now very few who are not receiving money.	Very few who are not receiving money	Envelopement al journalism
Line 1016	P 4	Some other journalists are already in the payroll of the city hall.	In the payroll of the city hall	Envelopement al journalism
Line 1474	P 8	In our station, first time you will be caught for envelopement al journalism you will be fired	You will be fired	Envelopement al journalism
Line 1410	P 8	Just imagine if you will interview 5 personalities, and you receive money from the 3 of them. You can decide to highlight the 3 and just kill the statements of the other 2.	Killing the 2 sides of the story	Envelopement al journalism
Line 1439	P 8	In a way, you shouldn't give a chance the society to suspect or doubt your objectivity and credibility.	Suspect or doubt your objectivity	Envelopement al journalism